

TRANSNATURE

Best practices on prevention and enforcement mechanisms against cross-border pollution and wildlife crime

TRANSNATURE (Biodiversa+)

Deliverable 3.2

Author: Digno Montalván Zambrano, Universitat Rovira i Virgili

Date: January 2026

This compendium of best practices has been authored by Digno Montalván-Zambrano (Universitat Rovira i Virgili). The author wishes to acknowledge Maria Marques-Banque and all project partners for providing their input for this document.

Content

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. BEST PRACTICES LED BY PUBLIC AUTHORITIES	7
2.1. Cooperation agreement between environmental agencies in the Julian Alps	8
2.2. Shared transboundary databases and digital reporting tools for wolverine monitoring	10
2.3. The Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment and Health (NKE)	12
2.4. Enhancing pollution prevention through coordinated transboundary governance in the Scheldt Estuary	14
2.5. Water Parliament: Annual cross-border forum for dialogue and cooperation on transboundary river management	16
2.6. Framework for transboundary cooperation on the management and conservation of wolverines in Fennoscandia	18
2.7. Julian Alps transboundary staff exchange program	20
2.8. Integrated approaches to contaminated site remediation and pollution prevention in the Baltic Sea Basin	22
2.9. Integrated governance and enforcement for marine and coastal Natura 2000 areas	24
3. BEST PRACTICES LED BY LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES	26
3.1. LIVEX-LOBO 2024: Cross-border simulation exercise focused on nature protection	27
3.2. Cross-border monitoring and targeted checks to combat illegal trade in wild bird eggs	30
3.3. Joint operational exercises to increase cross-border law-enforcement capacity for biodiversity protection	31
3.4. Coordinated cross-border enforcement to prevent poaching and biodiversity crime in the Danube River	33
3.5. Strengthening cross-border law-enforcement capacity for biodiversity protection in the Bihor–Hajdú-Bihar Euroregion	35
4. BEST PRACTICES LED BY NON-STATE ACTORS	37
4.1. Integrated environmental crime enforcement and intelligence model for biodiversity protection	38
4.2. Building capacity and cooperation to combat illegal bird crime along European migratory flyways	41
4.3. SWiPE project: strengthening wildlife crime prosecution through evidence, capacity building and cross-border cooperation in Europe	43
4.4. Cross-border environmental monitoring of the Danube River using integrated aerial, river-based, and renewable-energy systems	46
5. BEST PRACTICES LED BY EUROPEAN COOPERATION NETWORKS	48
5.1. TransParcNet Annual Meetings <i>European network for cooperation and knowledge exchange among transboundary protected areas</i>	49
5.2. European Network of Environmental Prosecutors (ENPE): strengthening cross-border prosecution of environmental crime	51
5.3. IMPEL: European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law	54
5.4. EUFJE: European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment	56
5.5. EnviCrimeNet: coordination and intelligence framework for combating environmental crime	59

1. INTRODUCTION

This document presents a compilation of 23 best practices on prevention and enforcement mechanisms against cross-border pollution and wildlife crimes. These practices have been identified, analyzed and systematized within the framework of Work Package (WP) 3 of the research project TRANSNATURE, Transboundary governance models of biodiversity protection, co-funded by the European Union in the framework of the European partnership *Biodiversa+*. The TRANSNATURE project examines how cross-border and transboundary governance arrangements can enhance biodiversity protection and contribute to preventing ecological degradation, including cross-border pollution and transnational wildlife crime. WP 3 focuses specifically on cross-border pollution and transnational wildlife crime, with the objective of assessing whether transboundary biodiversity conservation initiatives within the project's case studies enable the development of concrete mechanisms for prevention and enforcement. Within this framework, the present compilation aims to provide evidence-based insights into effective practices operating across national borders that strengthen cooperation, enforcement capacity, and institutional coordination in addressing pollution and wildlife crime.

The best practices included in this compilation operate within a European territorial context and involve EU Member States. They all have a clear transboundary dimension, understood as cooperative actions addressing environmental challenges that affect shared ecosystems, border regions, or interconnected territories across national boundaries. These include bilateral or trilateral border regions, shared protected areas, river basins, marine and coastal areas, and ecological corridors where environmental pressures and illegal activities extend beyond a single national jurisdiction. Only practices with concrete and operational transboundary cooperation mechanisms were included; initiatives with an international dimension but lacking a clear territorial and operational transboundary focus were excluded.

The good practices presented in this document were identified through three main sources. First, empirical research conducted within the four TRANSNATURE case studies¹, combining qualitative document analysis with semi-structured interviews. Second, a systematic review of 156 LIFE projects retrieved from the official LIFE Program database using the search terms “cross-border” and “transboundary”². Third, a comprehensive review of 4,109 Interreg projects identified through the KEEP database³ under the Green Europe thematic priority, from which projects incorporating objectives related to the prevention and enforcement of pollution and wildlife crime were analyzed in detail. In sum, the good practices were selected based on clearly defined criteria, including the presence of concrete cross-border cooperation mechanisms, a European scope of application, and demonstrated relevance for environmental crime prevention and enforcement.

¹ TRANSNATURE case studies are: 1) Julian Alps, Triglav National Park (Slovenia) and the Prealpi Giulie Natural Park (Italy); 2) ZASNET EGTC and transboundary biosphere reserve Meseta Ibérica, at the North-Eastern border of Portugal and Spain; 3) The western and northern border regions of Lappi and the neighboring areas in Sweden and Norway, and 4) The Scheldt Estuary, situated between the southwest of the Netherlands and the northwest of Flanders, Belgium. See <https://www.transnature.eu/>.

² <https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/search>.

³ <https://keep.eu/projects/>.

To enhance analytical clarity and practical usability, the best practices have been systematized primarily according to the type of organization leading the action, reflecting the diversity of actors involved in transboundary environmental governance and enforcement. These include practices led by public authorities, law enforcement agencies, and non-state actors. Public authorities are understood as governmental or administrative bodies at local, regional, national, or supranational levels that are responsible for managing public affairs, implementing policies, or overseeing specific domains such as environmental protection and biodiversity conservation. This category includes supranational, national, regional, and local governments; public agencies and regulatory bodies; environmental or park management organizations; and fire services and emergency response units.

Although law enforcement agencies are formally part of the public administration, they are treated as a distinct category in this analysis. Law enforcement agencies are public bodies specifically mandated to enforce laws through coercive means. They are empowered to investigate, intervene, and impose criminal or administrative sanctions under a legal mandate. This category includes police forces, border control authorities, customs services, and specialized units with investigative and sanctioning powers. While some public authorities, such as environmental agencies, may possess sanctioning competences, they are not classified as law enforcement agencies unless they directly exercise coercive enforcement powers, for example through inspections, fines, or detentions.

Finally, non-state actors include organizations that are not part of the public administration but play a relevant role in the prevention and enforcement of pollution and wildlife crime in transboundary contexts. This category primarily encompasses non-governmental organizations, universities, research institutions, professional associations, and civil society organizations. In the best practices analyzed, non-state actors frequently act as initiators or coordinators of transboundary actions, often working in close cooperation with public authorities and law enforcement agencies by contributing technical expertise, scientific knowledge, training activities, awareness-raising actions, or coordination and support functions.

In addition, a fourth group of best practices led by transboundary and European cooperation networks is identified. These networks are typically structured as non-profit associations or non-profit cooperation platforms that do not exercise direct regulatory or enforcement powers. Instead, they play a strategic role in facilitating coordination, professional exchange, institutional alignment, and mutual learning among authorities and practitioners operating across national borders. By providing permanent or recurrent platforms for interaction, these networks contribute to the harmonization of practices, the diffusion of expertise, and the strengthening of professional communities involved in the prevention and enforcement of pollution and wildlife crime in transboundary contexts. This group includes the European Network of Environmental Prosecutors (ENPE)⁴; EnviCrimeNet⁵, a network of environmental crime experts and law enforcement practitioners focusing on intelligence sharing, strategic analysis, and coordinated responses to serious and organized environmental crime; the European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment (EUFJE)⁶, which promotes judicial cooperation, training, and dialogue among judges dealing with environmental matters; and IMPEL – the European

⁴ See: <https://www.environmentalprosecutors.eu/>.

⁵ See: <https://www.envicrimenet.eu/>.

⁶ See: <https://www.eufje.org/index.php?lang=en>.

Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law⁷, which supports environmental authorities through peer-to-peer learning, joint projects, inspections, and guidance on the effective implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation. The group also includes TransParcNet⁸, the transboundary cooperation network of protected areas within the EUROPARC Federation, whose annual meetings provide a dedicated forum for exchange and coordination among managers of transboundary protected areas, fostering joint approaches to conservation, governance, and enforcement challenges affecting shared natural spaces.

In addition to this lead actor-based systematization, each best practice is also classified according to its primary functional dimension. Three functional categories are distinguished: planning and coordination (indicated in green in the title), enforcement action (indicated in blue), and information exchange and training (indicated in orange). While several of the good practices pursue multiple objectives and often combine elements of planning, enforcement, and capacity building within the same initiative, each practice has been categorized under a single functional dimension for analytical clarity. This classification is based on the dimension that represents the main objective or the most prominent operational focus of the practice, considering its core activities, governance arrangements, and intended outcomes. Practices classified under planning and coordination include strategic frameworks, joint governance structures, and institutional arrangements that enable sustained and long-term transboundary cooperation. Enforcement action practices focus on concrete operational measures, such as joint patrols, coordinated inspections, monitoring activities, investigations, and enforcement operations aimed at preventing and responding to pollution and wildlife crime. Finally, information exchange and training practices encompass shared databases, digital tools, capacity-building programs, professional training activities, and structured knowledge-sharing mechanisms that support learning, harmonization of practices, and institutional capacity across borders.

By bringing together this diverse set of experiences, this compilation illustrates how multi-level, multi-actor and cross-sectoral cooperation can strengthen transboundary biodiversity governance and enhance the prevention and enforcement of pollution and wildlife crime. Rather than promoting a single governance model, the good practices demonstrate a range of adaptable solutions that respond to different ecological, legal, and institutional contexts while addressing shared transboundary challenges. This document is intended to support policymakers, practitioners, and researchers by offering transferable lessons, success factors, and practical insights that can inform future initiatives aimed at protecting biodiversity across borders in Europe.

⁷ See: <https://impel.eu/>.

⁸ See: <https://www.europarc.org/transboundary-parks-programme/transparcnet/>.

2. BEST PRACTICES LED BY PUBLIC AUTHORITIES

Administrative and governance-driven approaches to
transboundary prevention and enforcement of
pollution and wildlife crime

2.1. Cooperation agreement between environmental agencies in the Julian Alps area

Country / Region Involved	Julian Alps Italy – Slovenia
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ARPA – Regional agency for the protection of the environment of Friuli Venezia Giulia (Italy) • ARSO – Slovenian agency for the environment
Partner Organization(s)	NOAVA - Operational Unit for Environmental Monitoring Activities of the Autonomous Region of Friuli-Venezia Giulia Slovenian rangers
Background and Context	<p>The environmental agencies of Friuli Venezia Giulia (ARPA) and Slovenia (ARSO) collaborate in the field of nature protection. This collaboration was formalized after the signature in March 2025 of a cooperation agreement to strengthen collaboration on both sides of the border.</p> <p>In addition to cooperation between law enforcement agencies, in the Friuli Venezia Giulia Region, NOAVA (Operational Unit for Environmental Surveillance) is active in the field of environmental offences (poaching, illegal waste disposal, illegal trade in animals, etc.) and maintains close relations with forest rangers and police across the border (e.g. combating poaching).</p> <p>The main challenges are the lack of comprehensive and complete data of phenomena of wildlife crime and pollution that have transboundary effects. Additionally, the mobility of species makes it necessary to monitor them across borders to maintain a favorable conservation status of protected species under the Habitats and Birds directives.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	The collaboration agreement covers a wide range of topics, from the quality of both marine and fresh water to air quality and meteorology and climatology, as well as laboratory analysis and soil quality. In particular, the collaboration involves the exchange of data in all environmental matters, the sharing of environmental archives, and activities for sharing and disseminating information, as well as the establishment of joint monitoring programs, including in the context of projects funded by the European Union.
Results and Achievements	This agreement provides a legal framework for various practices that were already in place on an informal basis. It improves coordination regarding the Isonzo—Soča river basin as it allows for a coordinated approach and data sharing regarding pollution levels. Following the agreement, ARPA has created a dedicated unit based in Gorizia on International relations and European project planning.
Success Factors	<p>The two environmental protection agencies have historically enjoyed a strong collaborative relationship, for example by exchanging meteorological and air quality data. Now, with this framework agreement, the collaboration will have an even more structured and, above all, cross-cutting context covering all environmental issues, promoting the necessary integrated approach to complex environmental issues.</p> <p>This partnership will take shape in particular through the exchange of data, the sharing of environmental archives, and the dissemination of information, as well</p>

	as through the establishment of joint monitoring programs, including in the context of projects funded by the European Union.
Challenges and Lessons Learned	Given that the agreement was only recently signed, it is still too early to draw conclusions about how it will work, although the signing of the agreement itself represents a decisive step toward greater cooperation, and the parties involved have expressed their satisfaction with it.
Transferability / Replicability	The collaboration that this practice entails could be replicated in order border regions, including also the border of Friuli Venezia Giulia with Austria.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.arpa.fvg.it/notizie-agenzia/arpa-fvg-e-arso-firmano-laccordo-di-cooperazione-sui-temi-ambientali/ • https://www.ilpiccolo.it/cronaca/inquinamento-gorizie-alleate-con-laccordo-arpa-arso-p71nl40k

2.2 Shared transboundary databases and digital reporting tools for wolverine monitoring

Country / Region Involved	Fennoscandian region Finland – Sweden – Norway
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland • Norwegian Environment Agency • Swedish Environmental Protection Agency
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National and regional wildlife management authorities • Research institutions from the three countries • Norwegian Institute for Nature Research • Field monitoring authorities and inspection services • Regional and county-level wildlife authorities • Civil society in general
Background and Context	<p>Historically, information flow and monitoring methodologies related to large carnivore management in Finland, Sweden, and Norway were primarily organized at national level, with limited cross-border exchange. As large carnivore populations expanded and cross-border movements became better documented, the need for coordinated transboundary cooperation increased.</p> <p>A first structured step was taken in 1991, when the Environmental Council of Northern Finland, Norway, and Sweden established a regional working group involving authorities from border regions in all three countries. The group developed coordinated monitoring approaches, connected field personnel through organized networks, supported joint research activities, and initiated more regular joint reporting on population status. In 1996, the three countries also established a coordinating group on large carnivore research.</p> <p>Political support for transboundary cooperation was formalized in 2011, when the responsible ministries in Finland, Norway, and Sweden signed a consensus statement on cooperation priorities for large carnivores. This agreement led to increased monitoring efforts and the establishment of shared data systems, including the Norwegian–Swedish large carnivore database (Rovbase) with reciprocal access. In 2012 a Memorandum of Understanding was signed regarding the establishment and continuance of a public web-based database (Skandobs) for geographic information on large carnivore observations in Norway and Sweden.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>Transboundary cooperation on wolverine monitoring is implemented through shared databases and digital reporting tools, primarily developed and operated by Sweden and Norway, with partial participation from Finland.</p> <p>Key components include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rovbase, a joint transboundary database used to register data on large carnivores, including observations, tracking efforts, reproductions, mortalities, damages, and DNA samples. Data are entered by authorized personnel through web interfaces, batch uploads, or mobile field applications. • Shared access to national databases, allowing authorities in Finland, Sweden, and Norway to consult relevant data in Rovbase, Tassu, and Riistavahinkorekisteri, in accordance with national legislation.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Public digital reporting tools, notably the Skandobs mobile application, which allows the public in Sweden and Norway to report observations and traces of large carnivores. Observations are verified by county-level authorities before inclusion in official monitoring data. Genetic data integration, whereby DNA analyses used to identify individuals and movements are registered in shared systems to support transboundary population assessment.
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The use of shared databases and digital reporting tools has enabled regular cross-border access to monitor data related to wolverine populations. Authorities can identify transboundary individuals, compare monitoring results, and coordinate population assessments using compatible datasets. Public reporting tools have increased the volume of reported observations, while verification procedures ensure that only validated data are included in official monitoring systems.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Formal agreements supporting data sharing and joint monitoring systems between Sweden and Norway. Use of common technical platforms for data storage and visualization. Clear verification procedures for citizen-reported observations. Gradual and incremental expansion of cooperation, allowing partial participation by additional countries. Funding availability.
Transferability / Replicability	The use of shared databases combined with digital field and public reporting tools is transferable to other transboundary wildlife populations. This model is applicable in contexts where species cross national borders and where coordinated monitoring, data verification, and information access are required across different administrative systems.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> https://www.rovbase.se/om https://www.skandobs.com/#showAbout https://www.naturvardsverket.se/4acc18/globalassets/amnen/jakt-och-vilt/dokument/framework-for-transboundary-cooperation-on-management-and-conservation-of-wolverines-in-fennoscandia.pdf

2.3. The Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment and Health (NKE)

Nordic cooperation on chemicals management under the Nordic Council of Ministers

Country / Region Involved	Nordic region Denmark – Finland – Iceland – Norway – Sweden
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment and Health (NKE) • Nordic Council of Ministers (Environment and Climate)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National chemicals and environmental authorities of the Nordic countries • Inspection and enforcement authorities • Research institutes and expert bodies supporting chemical risk assessment and monitoring
Background and Context	<p>The Nordic Council of Ministers is the official intergovernmental cooperation body of the Nordic countries, established to promote coordinated policies and practical cooperation across a wide range of sectors, including environment, climate, health, and sustainable development. It provides a political and administrative framework for joint Nordic initiatives, while implementation is carried out through specialized working groups composed of national authorities and experts.</p> <p>Within this structure, the Nordic Working Group for Chemicals, Environment and Health (NKE) operates under the Nordic Council of Ministers for Environment and Climate. NKE serves as a permanent cooperation platform for coordinating policies, enforcement practices, scientific assessments, and information exchange related to chemicals management.</p> <p>Chemical regulation in the Nordic countries is governed by EU legislation, international conventions, and national laws. While these frameworks provide common objectives, effective implementation requires close coordination between authorities to ensure consistent enforcement, reliable risk assessments, and early identification of hazardous and emerging substances. NKE addresses these needs by facilitating structured and long-term cooperation among the Nordic countries.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>NKE structures Nordic cooperation on chemicals management through specialized and complementary mechanisms, which together support coherent implementation of chemicals legislation and policy. These mechanisms involve national authorities, enforcement bodies, and scientific institutions and are designed to address different stages of the chemicals policy cycle. Between those specialized mechanisms are:</p> <p>Nordic Enforcement Group (NEG) The Nordic Enforcement Group coordinates joint enforcement activities related to chemicals legislation and product safety requirements. Authorities exchange inspection results, develop common interpretations of legislation, and carry out coordinated controls, including on cross-border trade and e-commerce.</p> <p>Nordic Pollutant Release and Transfer Register (PRTR) Authorities exchange experiences on data collection, quality assurance, reporting methodologies, and public access to PRTR information. This cooperation improves the comparability and transparency of data on industrial emissions and pollutant transfers, supports compliance with international reporting obligations, and enhances the use of PRTR data for environmental policy and chemicals management.</p> <p>Nordic Risk Assessment (NORAP)</p>

	<p>Nordic Risk Assessment cooperation enables countries to share expertise and workload related to human health and environmental risk assessments. Joint or coordinated assessments support consistency in scientific evaluations and strengthen Nordic contributions to EU-level and international risk management processes.</p> <p>Nordic Screening of Chemicals</p> <p>Nordic Screening of Chemicals consists of coordinated monitoring studies designed to identify hazardous and emerging substances in the environment. Screening results provide early warning signals and support prioritization of substances for further assessment or regulatory action.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of coordinated Nordic enforcement projects, leading to more consistent application of chemicals legislation across countries. • Delivery of joint or coordinated risk assessments, strengthening scientific input to EU and international chemicals processes. • Identification of hazardous and emerging substances through Nordic screening activities, supporting early policy responses. • Improved quality, transparency, and comparability of PRTR data, enhancing reporting on pollutant releases and transfers and supporting evidence-based environmental policy. • Strengthened cooperation and knowledge exchange among national authorities, enforcement bodies, and research institutions across the Nordic region.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional anchoring within the Nordic Council of Ministers, providing political legitimacy and long-term continuity. • Clear division of roles among specialized working mechanisms (enforcement, risk assessment, screening, and PRTR). • Practical focus on activities that complement national responsibilities rather than replace them.
<p>Challenges and Lessons Learned</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in national administrative structures and legal interpretations require continuous coordination. • Resource constraints necessitate prioritization of joint activities and careful allocation of expertise. • Maintaining alignment with evolving EU legislation and international obligations requires ongoing adaptation. • Coordinating data quality and reporting practices across countries remains a continuous effort.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.norden.org/en/publication/nordic-co-operation-chemicals-environment-and-health • https://pub.norden.org/politiknord2024-725/politiknord2024-725.pdf • https://www.norden.org/en/nordic-council-ministers

2.4. Enhancing pollution prevention through coordinated transboundary governance in the Scheldt Estuary	
Country / Region Involved	Scheldt estuary cross-border region The Netherlands – Flanders (Belgium)
Lead Organization(s)	Flemish–Dutch Scheldt Commission (VNSC) (in the context of policy coordination and management of the Scheldt Estuary)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flemish Department of Environment and Spatial Development • Flemish Environment Agency (VMM) • Dutch Ministry of Infrastructure and Water Management • Rijkswaterstaat • Scheldt Council (multi-stakeholder advisory platform) • Relevant regional environmental and permitting authorities
Background and Context	<p>The Scheldt estuary is a shared transboundary estuary between the Netherlands and Flanders (Belgium). The Netherlands and Belgium apply diverging national standards and permitting procedures, and regulatory approaches have increasingly highlighted the need for greater harmonization. Recent discussions—and in some cases legal disputes—related to e.g. nitrogen emissions, PFAS (Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances) contamination, and other industrial pollutants have revealed gaps in coordination across the Dutch–Flemish border. These issues often concern emissions authorized in one country that can have measurable environmental impacts in the neighboring country, for example PFAS discharges, where differing national limit values and permitted thresholds further complicate coordinated risk management.</p> <p>These differences create risks of regulatory inconsistencies, cross-border environmental impacts, and administrative inefficiencies. Although a fully established good practice for joint permitting or harmonized pollutant standards does not yet exist, current cooperation mechanisms provide a crucial foundation for improved alignment.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>While cooperation is carried out with the focus on the policy and management of the Scheldt estuary, pollution does not fall under this mandate. However, as part of this cooperation mechanisms, the different agencies and departments from the Netherlands and Flanders have regular communications, including on the impacts of pollution. This means that the current communication channels can be viewed as starting point for transboundary communication.</p> <p>Overall (in the context of management of the area), the following actions have been implemented – that can have a positive spill over on the pollution debate:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened communication channels between Dutch and Flemish authorities through the Flemish-Dutch Scheldt Commission and its working groups. • Regular cross-border technical consultations on estuarine water quality, emission trends, and pollution sources (part of mandate International Scheldt Commission). • Use of existing cooperation frameworks, including the Scheldt Council, to ensure structured dialogue between governments, agencies, and stakeholders.

<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<p>General results and achievements that can have spillover effect on transboundary pollution:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased mutual awareness of planned activities and emerging pollution challenges in the estuary. • More frequent and transparent coordination among agencies responsible for monitoring, regulation, and permitting. • Enhanced trust and institutional relationships, improving the overall capacity for joint problem-solving. <p>Although not yet fully formalized, these developments represent incremental progress toward more coherent transboundary pollution prevention in the Scheldt region.</p>
<p>Success Factors</p>	<p>Success factors under this transboundary cooperation mechanism that can have spillover effects on transboundary pollution include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established governance platforms (Scheldt Council) providing continuity and legitimacy. Also, the International Scheldt Commission is relevant to mention in this context (mandate in the field of the Water Framework Directive). • Commitment of national and regional authorities to maintain regular cross-border dialogue. • Technical expertise and monitoring data exchanged between agencies, enabling more informed decision-making. • Shared recognition of the estuary as a single ecological system requiring coordinated management.
<p>Challenges and Lessons Learned</p>	<p>As said, pollution does not fall under the VNSC mandate. However, pollution (e.g. PFAS) was regularly mentioned as a concern for many of the involved agencies/stakeholders, referring to various challenges:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in pollutant standards and legal frameworks (e.g., nitrogen, PFAS) make harmonization complex and slow. • Permit procedures are still predominantly national, occasionally resulting in uncoordinated decisions with cross-border implications. • Institutional fragmentation on both sides of the border can hinder timely information exchange. • Experience shows that early consultation and structured dialogue can help prevent disputes and reduce the risk of legal challenges. • Reinforcing cooperation mechanisms can improve predictability for authorities and stakeholders, decreasing the likelihood of cross-border litigation.
<p>Transferability / Replicability</p>	<p>The approach—strengthening existing cross-border institutions, increasing systematic communication, and aligning procedures step-by-step—is highly transferable to other transboundary river basins and/or estuaries where meaningful transboundary cooperation / governance is not yet achieved. This can be particularly relevant for regions with complex regulatory landscapes, shared ecological systems, and high industrial activity.</p>
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://vnsc.eu/

2.5. Water Parliament

Annual cross-border forum for dialogue and cooperation on transboundary river management

Country / Region Involved	Finnish–Swedish transboundary river area Torne Valley (or Meänmaa) Finland – Sweden
Lead Organization(s)	Finnish-Swedish Transboundary River Commission
Partner Organization(s)	Ministries in Finland and Sweden, regional authorities, researchers, local citizens in the Finnish-Swedish transboundary area (Torne Valley), general public.
Background and Context	<p>The Tornionjoki River Basin is one of the largest transboundary river basins shared by Finland and Sweden, covering an area of 40,157 km². Approximately 60% of the basin lies in Sweden, with the remaining part in Finland and a small upstream area in Norway.</p> <p>The basin is designated as part of the Natura 2000 network, in accordance with the EU Habitats Directive, and is subject to the implementation of the EU Water Framework Directive (2000/60/EC), which entered into force in December 2000 and has been transposed into national legislation in both Finland and Sweden. These frameworks require coordinated planning, monitoring, and management of shared water bodies.</p> <p>To support this coordination, the Finnish–Swedish Transboundary River Commission was established as a joint body appointed by the Government of Finland and the Swedish Government. Each country appoints three members and their deputies, supported by permanent experts in fisheries and water management. The Commission is responsible for promoting cooperation between Finnish and Swedish authorities, coordinating water management programs and plans, monitoring the status of waters, and issuing joint opinions on permits and measures affecting transboundary rivers and coastal waters.</p> <p>The Commission also ensures the provision of joint information and public hearings related to transboundary river management and overseas joint monitoring activities, including annual summaries of coordinated monitoring of the Tornionjoki and Muonionjoki rivers. Within this institutional framework, regular stakeholder engagement and information exchange are organized to support the preparation and implementation of water management plans and action programs, including those for the planning cycles 2022–2027 and 2027–2033.</p> <p>This context forms the basis for the Water Parliament, which functions as a recurring platform for dialogue and cooperation among authorities, experts, and stakeholders involved in the management of the Finnish–Swedish transboundary river area.</p>
Description of Activities /	The Water Parliament is organized as a one-day annual event in the Finnish–Swedish transboundary river area of the Tornionjoki River Basin. The event is coordinated by the Finnish–Swedish Transboundary River Commission and is open to authorities, experts, stakeholders, and the public from both countries.

<p>Actions Implemented</p>	<p>The Water Parliament provides a structured setting for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presentations by authorities and experts on water management, monitoring results, environmental status, and implementation of water management plans related to the transboundary river basin. • Information exchange on programs, measures, and planning cycles linked to the EU Water Framework Directive and related national and bilateral frameworks. • Joint discussion sessions, allowing participants from Finland and Sweden to address shared water-related issues, planned measures, and their cross-border implications. • Stakeholder engagement, including the participation of regional and local authorities, researchers, and residents from the Tornio Valley, supporting transparency and public involvement in transboundary water governance. <p>The Water Parliament complements the Commission’s ongoing work on joint monitoring, planning, and coordination by providing a recurring forum for dialogue and dissemination of information related to the management of the shared river basin.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<p>The implementation of the Water Parliament has contributed to regular information exchange between Finnish and Swedish authorities, experts, and stakeholders involved in the management of the Tornionjoki River Basin. The event supports the dissemination of joint monitoring results, water status assessments, and updates on water management plans and action programs applicable to the transboundary river basin.</p> <p>Through annual meetings, the Water Parliament facilitates coordination between national and regional actors, enabling the identification of shared issues and the alignment of measures affecting the transboundary waters.</p> <p>The forum also ensures public access to information and stakeholder participation in accordance with the requirements of the EU Water Framework Directive and national legislation, contributing to transparency in transboundary water governance.</p>
<p>Success factors</p>	<p>The existence of the Finnish–Swedish Transboundary River Commission as a joint institutional body ensures continuity, coordination capacity, and linkage between the Water Parliament and ongoing transboundary planning, monitoring, and decision-making processes.</p> <p>The open participation of national, regional, and local authorities, researchers, and residents supports broad stakeholder involvement and the dissemination of information across different governance levels.</p>
<p>Transferability / Replicability</p>	<p>The model is compatible with the implementation requirements of the EU Water Framework Directive and can be adapted to different hydrological, administrative, and institutional settings within and beyond the European Union.</p>
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.fsgk.se/fi/suomalais-ruotsalainen-rajajokikomissio/ • https://www.fsgk.se/fi/tornionlaakson-vesiparlamentti-2025/ • https://www.fsgk.se/fi/vesiparlamentti/

2.6. Framework for transboundary cooperation on the management and conservation of wolverines in Fennoscandia	
Country / Region Involved	Fennoscandian region Finland – Sweden – Norway
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland • Norwegian Environment Agency • Swedish Environmental Protection Agency
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Regional wildlife management authorities • Research institutions • Field monitoring and inspection services
Background and Context	<p>Historically, large carnivore monitoring and management in Finland, Sweden, and Norway were organized primarily through national systems, with limited cross-border information exchange. As wolverine populations expanded and their transboundary movements became better documented, national approaches proved insufficient for population-level management.</p> <p>An initial step towards transboundary cooperation was taken in 1991, when regional authorities from the three countries established a working group to coordinate monitoring and reporting of large carnivore populations. This cooperation expanded during the 1990s, including the establishment of a trilateral research coordination group in 1996.</p> <p>Political support for coordinated management was formalized in 2011 through the Agreement between the Ministry of Agriculture and Forestry of Finland, the Norwegian Ministry of Environment, and the Swedish Ministry of Environment on developing collaboration on large carnivores (brown bear, wolf, lynx, and wolverine). This agreement led to increased monitoring efforts, the development of shared databases, and formal arrangements for data sharing and joint reporting. The need for transboundary cooperation was further supported by the work of the Large Carnivore Initiative for Europe, which highlighted population-level management as a key requirement for large carnivore conservation.</p> <p>These developments culminated in the adoption of the Framework for Transboundary Cooperation on the Management and Conservation of Wolverines in Fennoscandia, signed by Finland, Sweden, and Norway in 2022. The Framework is the second trilateral cooperation document between the three countries and was developed through close collaboration between relevant management institutions, with expert input from the Fennoscandian Wolverine Workshops organized under the LIFE Euro LargeCarnivores project.</p> <p>The Framework provides a structured basis for ongoing bilateral and trilateral cooperation. It is subject to periodic evaluation and revision every six years, in line with the reporting cycles of the EU Habitats Directive and is valid through 2028. While Finland and Sweden are bound by the EU Habitats Directive as EU Member States, Norway participates under the Bern Convention, reflecting the need for coordination across different legal frameworks.</p>
Description of Activities /	The Framework structures transboundary cooperation through established mechanisms at administrative, management, research, and field levels.

<p>Actions Implemented</p>	<p>Administrative coordination is ensured through at least one annual bilateral or trilateral meeting, where national authorities exchange information on policy developments, management measures, and research outcomes. Additional meetings are organized when specific needs arise, supported by a shared digital workspace for official documents.</p> <p>Management coordination addresses differences in national management systems, including contrasting population goals and the effects of source–sink dynamics in border regions. Authorities exchange information to support coordinated decision-making and reduce unintended cross-border impacts.</p> <p>Research cooperation includes coordination of research priorities and joint or co-financed projects focused on population dynamics, genetics, connectivity, and ecological processes relevant to transboundary management.</p> <p>Field-level cooperation involves regular coordination between field personnel in border regions to align practices related to monitoring, damage documentation, and management actions. Occasional cross-border field activities are conducted to optimize resources and improve tracking of transboundary individuals.</p> <p>Compensation and conflict mitigation are integral components of the Framework. Each country operates national compensation schemes for damages caused by wolverines, particularly in relation to reindeer herding and extensive livestock grazing. The Framework promotes information exchange on compensation models and their interaction with management measures, recognizing compensation as a key tool for conflict mitigation and social acceptance.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a formal trilateral framework for coordinated wolverine management. • Regularized administrative, scientific, and operational cooperation across national borders. • Improved coordination of management actions in transboundary areas. • Enhanced exchange of knowledge related to population dynamics and conflict mitigation.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Long-term, incremental development of cooperation based on earlier regional initiatives. • Formal political endorsement through intergovernmental agreements. • Integration of management, research, and field-level coordination within a single framework. • Recognition of compensation mechanisms as part of transboundary management.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.naturvardsverket.se/4acc18/globalassets/amnen/jakt-och-vilt/dokument/framework-for-transboundary-cooperation-on-management-and-conservation-of-wolverines-in-fennoscandia.pdf • https://pub.norden.org/nord2025-006/files/67dbd7647a299_no2025-006_transfrontier_collaboration_fennoscandia_combat_wildlife_crime.pdf

2.7. Julian Alps transboundary staff exchange program

Long-term cross-border staff exchange fostering cooperation and mutual understanding

Country / Region Involved	Julian Alps Italy – Slovenia
Lead Organization(s)	Protected area management authorities of the Julian Alps Transboundary Area
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Protected area staff and technical teams from both sides of the Julian Alps Local and regional stakeholders involved in protected area management and sustainable tourism Partners participating in the EUROPARC European Charter for Sustainable Tourism (ECST) framework
Background and Context	<p>The management of the Julian Alps transboundary protected area requires stable cooperation between protected area authorities, public administrations, local communities, and the tourism sector across national borders. To respond to this need, cooperation in the area has progressively been structured through permanent and practice-based mechanisms that support joint planning, implementation, and stakeholder engagement.</p> <p>Within this framework, the ECST Annual Forum functions as a permanent participatory platform, established under the European Charter for Sustainable Tourism (ECST). The forum brings together protected area authorities, national and regional bodies, local municipalities, conservation and community organizations, and representatives of the tourism industry. Organized annually on a rotating basis between Italy and Slovenia, it provides a structured space for dialogue, coordination, and joint action in support of sustainable tourism and nature conservation.</p> <p>The transboundary staff exchange program is closely connected to this forum-based cooperation model. Staff exchanges are designed to reinforce the objectives discussed within the ECST Annual Forum by translating strategic dialogue into direct professional interaction and practical collaboration. Through regular exchanges and joint participation in forums and related activities, staff members develop a shared understanding of management approaches, governance structures, and local contexts on both sides of the border.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>The Julian Alps Transboundary Staff Exchange Program is implemented through regular exchanges and joint activities that bring together protected area staff, stakeholders, and partners from both the Italian and Slovenian sides of the Julian Alps. The program is closely linked to the ECST Annual Forum, which provides a stable framework for structured interaction, knowledge exchange, and joint reflection on conservation and sustainable tourism.</p> <p>Through staff exchanges, joint meetings, and participation in annual forums, the initiative fosters the creation of a well-informed and well-connected transboundary network of professionals and stakeholders. These exchanges</p>

	combine formal discussions with practical learning, including visits to local best practices in nature conservation, sustainable tourism, cultural heritage, and quality branding.
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of strong interpersonal networks among protected area staff across the border. • Improved mutual understanding of administrative systems, management tools, and operational practices. • Enhanced capacity for joint planning and coordinated action in conservation and sustainable tourism. • Increased effectiveness of transboundary cooperation through smoother communication and problem-solving at operational level.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuity over time, with the program running annually since 2015. • Strong emphasis on personal contact and trust-building at staff level. • Practical, hands-on exchanges embedded in real management activities. • Alignment with broader cooperation frameworks, particularly the ECST, ensuring strategic coherence.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.europarc.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Practical-Guidelines-for-TBA-Managers-2024-1.pdf

2.8. Integrated approaches to contaminated site remediation and pollution prevention in the Baltic Sea Basin

Country / Region Involved	Central Baltic / Baltic Sea Region Sweden – Finland – Latvia
Lead Organization(s)	County Administrative Board of Östergötland (Länsstyrelsen Östergötland), Sweden
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motala Municipality, Sweden • University of Helsinki, Finland • Latvian Environment, Geology and Meteorology Centre, Latvia • Vidzeme Planning Region, Latvia • Valmiera City Council, Latvia • Populus Group Oy, Finland (partner during 2015–2018)
Background and Context	<p>The Baltic Sea is particularly vulnerable to pollution due to its limited water exchange and the cumulative impact of land-based sources. Contaminated sites represent a persistent source of hazardous substances entering groundwater, surface waters, and ultimately the marine environment. Across Sweden, Finland, and Latvia, many such sites originate from historical industrial and municipal activities and involve complex contamination affecting soil, groundwater, sediments, and built structures.</p> <p>Traditionally, excavation and off-site disposal have been the dominant remediation methods. While effective in removing contaminants, these approaches generate significant greenhouse gas emissions and high costs due to the transport of contaminated and clean materials. As a result, remediation efforts have often been slow, infrequent, and environmentally burdensome. Authorities have also faced challenges related to prioritization of contaminated sites, limited availability of sustainable alternatives, and the need for more effective supervision and enforcement mechanisms.</p> <p>Within this context, the Innovative Sustainable Remediation (INSURE) project was developed under the Interreg Central Baltic Program as a cross-border cooperation between Sweden, Finland, and Latvia. Running from 2015 to 2019, INSURE aimed to reduce the distribution of hazardous substances into the Baltic Sea by making remediation of contaminated sites both more frequent and more sustainable, while strengthening governance tools and technical capacity.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice demonstrates an integrated model that combines sustainable remediation technologies, strengthened supervision and enforcement, and innovative visualization tools, implemented through structured cross-border cooperation.</p> <p>1. Sustainable In Situ Remediation through Pilot Testing</p> <p>INSURE tested cost-effective and environmentally sustainable in situ remediation methods as alternatives to excavation. Eight pilot areas across Sweden, Finland, and Latvia were selected, each characterized by different historical contaminants and site conditions.</p> <p>The tested techniques included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Biostimulation. • Electrokinetic pumping. • Fenton reaction. • Phytoremediation.

	<p>By applying these methods directly at contaminated sites, the project reduced the need for material transport and associated CO₂ emissions. The pilots generated practical knowledge on which techniques are suitable for specific types of contamination, contributing to best-practice guidance for sustainable remediation.</p> <p>2. Supervision and Enforcement as Drivers of Remediation</p> <p>The project developed and tested new approaches to supervision and enforcement, enabling authorities to increase the remediation rate of contaminated sites.</p> <p>Key measures included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of handbooks, checklists, and methodologies for supervision and enforcement in operation. • Strategies for managing complex sites involving multiple contaminants, large areas, or fragmented ownership. • Introduction of structured self-monitoring mechanisms for enterprises responsible for contaminated sites. <p>A practical Plan of Action for enterprise self-monitoring was developed and piloted in Sweden, involving the County Administrative Board of Östergötland, Motala Municipality, and 28 enterprises.</p> <p>3. Technical Tools for Visualization and Decision Support</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of a national contaminated sites database in Latvia; • GIS-based visualization tools to support prioritization, risk assessment, and planning.
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increased application of sustainable in situ remediation methods. • Reduced potential leakage of hazardous substances into the Baltic Sea. • Strengthened supervision and enforcement capacity of environmental authorities. • Improved compliance through enterprise self-monitoring mechanisms. • Enhanced prioritization and transparency through databases and GIS tools. • Practical cross-border knowledge exchange between Sweden, Finland, and Latvia.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong cross-border cooperation among authorities, municipalities, research institutions, and private actors. • Use of pilot sites to generate applied and transferable evidence. • Active involvement of enterprises in self-monitoring and remediation processes.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://database.centralbaltic.eu/project/6.html • https://database.centralbaltic.eu/sites/default/files/Insure%20Broschure.pdf

2.9. Integrated governance and enforcement for marine and coastal Natura 2000 areas

Country / Region Involved	Adriatic Sea coastal and marine Natura 2000 sites Italy – Croatia
Lead Organization(s)	Association for Nature, Environment and Sustainable Development Sunce
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Municipality of Ugento • Interreg VI-A Italy–Croatia Programme 2021–2027
Background and Context	<p>Coastal and marine ecosystems play a critical role in biodiversity conservation, climate regulation, and the livelihoods of coastal communities. In the European Union, many of these ecosystems are protected under the Natura 2000 network, the largest coordinated network of protected areas in the world, established to safeguard habitats and species of European importance.</p> <p>While strong legal frameworks exist at both EU and national levels to protect Natura 2000 sites, ensuring effective on-the-ground management remains a major challenge. In marine and coastal environments, this challenge is particularly acute due to the complexity of governance: multiple institutions often share responsibilities for surveillance, enforcement, maritime safety, fisheries, and environmental protection. As a result, everyday human activities—such as illegal fishing, uncontrolled anchoring, coastal fires, and unregulated tourism—continue to negatively affect protected sites. The Adriatic Sea is a shared marine basin between Italy and Croatia, meaning environmental pressures and illegal activities frequently transcend national borders. Isolated national responses are therefore insufficient. Cross-border cooperation is essential to ensure consistent surveillance, coordinated enforcement, and shared standards for protecting marine and coastal Natura 2000 sites.</p> <p>Within this context, the Interreg VI-A Italy–Croatia Program provides a framework to strengthen, between others, institutional cooperation and governance of shared natural resources. The EFFICIENTN2K project was developed to address these challenges by improving collaboration among institutions responsible for surveillance and enforcement in coastal and marine Natura 2000 areas.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice focuses on building durable institutional cooperation between Italian and Croatian authorities involved in surveillance and enforcement of marine and coastal protected areas.</p> <p>The project began with a comprehensive review of legal and institutional frameworks in both countries to identify gaps, overlaps, and weaknesses in existing surveillance and enforcement systems. This analysis highlighted structural barriers that limit effective control of human activities affecting Natura 2000 sites.</p> <p>Based on these findings, the project organized cross-border workshops and stakeholder consultations, bringing together environmental agencies, maritime and port authorities, legal experts, local governments, and enforcement bodies. These workshops served as a platform to jointly discuss challenges and co-design practical solutions.</p> <p>Key actions included the development and testing of collaborative enforcement solutions, such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New forms of institutional cooperation between enforcement bodies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Joint surveillance approaches in marine and coastal Natura 2000 sites. • Measures to regulate anchoring and reduce damage to seabeds. • Improved fire prevention practices in coastal areas. • A catalogue of best practices to reduce illegal fishing. <p>A distinctive feature of the project was the implementation of joint demonstrative surveillance actions in selected Natura 2000 sites. These pilot activities showcased how coordinated cross-border collaboration can increase enforcement efficiency and improve protection outcomes in real operational conditions.</p> <p>The cooperation framework was formalized through the signing of a joint declaration, committing Italian and Croatian institutions to continued collaboration beyond the project's lifetime. This declaration serves as a roadmap for future cooperation, projects, and funding initiatives.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strengthened cooperation between Italian and Croatian institutions responsible for marine and coastal enforcement. • Improved surveillance and enforcement practices targeting illegal fishing, uncontrolled anchoring, and coastal fires. • Development of a joint action plan for surveillance and enforcement in Natura 2000 sites. • Adoption of legal, administrative, and operational recommendations for improved governance. • Formal commitment to future cooperation through an administrative agreement. • Increased awareness among decision-makers and stakeholders about enforcement challenges in marine protected areas.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong cross-border framework provided by the Interreg VI-A Italy–Croatia Program. • Inclusive, multi-institutional approach involving enforcement bodies, environmental authorities, and legal experts. • Combination of legal analysis, capacity building, and practical field demonstrations. • High level of stakeholder engagement and trust-building between institutions. • Clear focus on actionable, operational solutions rather than purely strategic documents.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.italy-croatia.eu/web/efficientn2k • https://www.italy-croatia.eu/documents/1131497/6382929/D2.2.1_Report_joint+actions.pdf/44c00a96-4ef9-0977-97c1-a7d8bd135968?t=1743414904816 • https://www.italy-croatia.eu/documents/1131497/4403833/D1.2.2.+Declaration+on+institutional+cooperation+in+implementing+solutions.pdf/d7d40872-5d2a-b0fe-0d49-2fff1782d373?t=1743415777142

3. BEST PRACTICES LED BY LAW ENFORCEMENT AGENCIES

Operational approaches to transboundary prevention
and enforcement of pollution and wildlife crime

3.1. LIVEX-LOBO 2024: Cross-border simulation exercise focused on nature protection

Country / Region Involved	Meseta Ibérica Spain – Portugal Cross-border area of Fermoselle (Zamora-Spain) and Mogadouro (Braganza-Portugal)
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Spain: Guardia Civil – Servicio de Protección de la Naturaleza (SEPRONA) • Portugal: Guarda Nacional Republicana – Serviço de Proteção da Natureza e do Ambiente (SEPNA) Operational Coordination: Chief Lieutenant of SEPRONA at the Zamora Command, María Isabel García.
Partner Organization(s)	Local authorities: Fermoselle City Council Local communities: Around 100 people mobilized, including organizers, participants, and role players. Residents of Fermoselle actively collaborated by reenacting scenarios to enhance the realism of the simulation exercises.
Background and Context	<p>In Spain and Portugal, the Guardia Civil and the Guarda Nacional Republicana (GNR) are the authorities responsible for ensuring compliance with regulations related to nature and environmental protection, including the conservation of water resources, wildlife, fisheries, forests, and other natural assets. In addition to their national mandates, both services are responsible for international environmental cooperation, working closely with organizations such as EUROPOL, INTERPOL, and various European institutions in the field of environmental protection. Their work has recently been recognized at European level as an example of success and innovation in environmental law enforcement.</p> <p>Building on this strong institutional role and on more than 20 years of sustained cross-border cooperation, the LIVEX-LOBO 2024 exercise was designed to train, refine, and strengthen interoperability between the SEPNA and SEPRONA structures. The initiative aimed to promote the exchange of knowledge, consolidate existing good practices, and further reinforce mutual trust between both services when addressing environmental incidents with potential cross-border impacts.</p>
Objectives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To train, enhance, and promote interoperability between the SEPNA and SEPRONA structures. • Fostering the exchange of knowledge and best practices, recognizing the interconnection of ecosystems, and enhancing international collaboration in tackling environmental crimes. • Fostering a preventive culture of cross-border environmental security, playing a key and proactive role in jointly addressing incidents that harm natural resources and biodiversity. • Development of joint strategic coordination frameworks to build alliances and promote multipolar solutions for addressing climate emergencies.

<p>Description of Activities / Actions Implemented</p>	<p>The LIVEX-LOBO 2024 exercise took place in the cross-border area of Fermoselle (Spain) and Mogadouro (Portugal), involving 60 officers from SEPRONA (Guardia Civil) and SEPNA (Guarda Nacional Republicana).</p> <p>Participating units from the Guardia Civil came from several Spanish provinces, while the GNR was represented by units from multiple Portuguese districts, ensuring broad territorial coverage. Exercise scenarios were intentionally located on both sides of the border, reflecting the transboundary nature of environmental incidents. Residents of Fermoselle took part as role players (e.g. poachers and illegal trappers), enhancing the realism of the simulations.</p> <p>The exercise comprised four operational scenarios addressing real environmental threats affecting both countries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poisoned baits: detection with canine units, sample collection, and full investigation procedures. • Pollution and illegal discharges: simulation of a cross-border pollution event, including sampling, damage mitigation, and investigation of responsibilities. • Forest fires: investigation of fire origin using documentation, satellite imagery, and on-site inspections. • Illegal trafficking: border controls and inspection of commercial consignments (e.g. wildlife products, gases, waste), applying relevant legal procedures.
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The exercise concluded with a joint demonstration of resources and a presentation of results to authorities from both countries. • A dedicated evaluation team assessed the actions carried out and identified areas for improvement. • The conclusions will inform the revision of existing collaboration plans and the Technical Procedure Guidelines of both services, strengthening future joint operations. • The exercise reinforced operational readiness and mutual understanding between the two forces.
<p>Success Factors</p>	<p>The effectiveness of LIVEX-LOBO 2024 is rooted in a long-standing history of cooperation between the Guardia Civil and the Guarda Nacional Republicana (GNR), built over almost two decades of sustained police collaboration in the cross-border area.</p> <p>A key enabling factor is the Centro de Cooperação Policial e Aduaneira de Quintanilha-Alcanices (CCPA), which serves as a permanent meeting point and coordination hub for Spanish and Portuguese police forces. As part of the European network of Police and Customs Cooperation Centers, the CCPA facilitates continuous information exchange, operational coordination, and mutual support in border control, customs, and law enforcement tasks. The center operates 24/7 with staff from the Policía Nacional, Guardia Civil, and Customs authorities, providing a solid institutional framework for cross-border cooperation.</p> <p>Within this framework, SEPRONA (Guardia Civil) and SEPNA (GNR) have carried out regular joint activities, including mixed patrols focused on environmental protection and forest fire prevention. This ongoing cooperation was further strengthened during the implementation of the LIVEX-LOBO 2024 exercise.</p> <p>Finally, the implementation of harmonized protocols for environmental crime investigation and sample collection—combining best practices from both police</p>

	forces—has significantly accelerated response times and improved the overall effectiveness of joint operations.
Challenges and Lessons Learned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • One of the main challenges identified during the exercise was telecommunications interoperability, as the use of different radio systems and national frequencies limited direct communication between teams. • At the same time, language was not identified as a significant obstacle, given the high level of familiarity and operational experience gained through years of cross-border cooperation between personnel from both countries. • The exercise highlighted the importance of harmonized communication protocols and interoperable technical solutions to strengthen coordination and effectiveness in cross-border environmental emergency response.
Transferability / Replicability	The relevance and potential replicability of the LIVEX-LOBO 2024 exercise were reinforced by the presence of international observers from Italy and France, as well as a dedicated evaluation team. Their participation highlights the interest in this model as a reference for cross-border environmental cooperation in other European border regions.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.interior.gob.es/opencms/va/detalle/articulo/EL-SEPRONA-y-el-SEPNA-de-la-Guardia-Nacional-Republicana-de-Portugal-realizan-un-ejercicio-transfronterizo-conjunto-en-el-ambito-de-la-proteccion-medioambiental/ • https://interbenavente.es/art/59381/fermoselle-acoge-el-simulacro-medioambiental-internacional-livex-lobo-2024-entre-espana-y-portugal • https://www.laopiniondezamora.es/comarcas/2024/11/15/fermoselle-escenario-ejercicio-internacional-actuar-111722957.html • https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=b_or-IX5Qg • https://www.facebook.com/reel/1372827080886882

3.2. Cross-border monitoring and targeted checks to combat illegal trade in wild bird eggs

Country / Region Involved	Northern Lapland border region Sweden – Norway – Finland
Lead Organization(s)	Law enforcement authorities operating in the northern border regions of Sweden, Norway, and Finland
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Police authorities • Border Guard services • Wilderness patrol units • Environmental and wildlife protection authorities
Background and Context	<p>The northern border areas of Sweden, Norway, and Finland are characterized by extensive and remote territories, which create favorable conditions for cross-border illegal activities related to wildlife. One recurrent challenge in this region has been the illegal trade of wild bird eggs, which exploits differences in accessibility, border permeability, and enforcement capacity across national jurisdictions.</p> <p>Given the transboundary nature of this illegal activity, isolated national enforcement actions proved insufficient. This situation prompted law enforcement authorities from the three countries to establish coordinated cross-border monitoring and control measures focused specifically on border crossings in the northern Lapland region.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>Law enforcement authorities from Sweden, Norway, and Finland organize annual coordinated monitoring operations at selected border crossing points and surrounding areas.</p> <p>These operations include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Targeted border checks focusing on routes and periods identified as high-risk illegal bird egg trafficking. • Joint planning and information exchange between national authorities prior to the monitoring activities. • Coordination among police, border guards, and wilderness patrols, ensuring coverage of both formal border crossings and remote border areas. <p>The monitoring activities are designed to both detect illegal activities and act as a deterrent, increasing the perceived risk for offenders engaged in cross-border wildlife crime.</p>
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved coordination and operational cooperation between law enforcement authorities across the three countries. • Reduction in reported incidents related to the illegal trade of wild bird eggs, as reported by participating authorities. • Increased capacity to detect and respond to wildlife-related crimes in remote border areas.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High level of trust between law enforcement authorities built through long-term cooperation. • Use of shared databases and information exchange mechanisms to support operational planning. • Regular implementation of monitoring activities, allowing authorities to refine approaches over time. • Involvement of specialized units familiar with wildlife crime and remote-area enforcement.

3.3. Joint operational exercises to increase cross-border law-enforcement capacity for biodiversity protection

Country / Region Involved	Maramureş, Satu Mare, Zakarpattia, Ivano-Frankivsk cross-border mountain and forest protected areas Romania – Ukraine
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inspectoratul de Jandarmi Judeţean Satu Mare (Satu Mare County Gendarmerie Inspectorate), Romania • Inspectoratul de Jandarmi Judeţean „Pintea Viteazul” Maramureş (Romania) • National Guard of Ukraine – Military Unit 1241 (Zakarpattia Region) • National Guard of Ukraine – units operating in Ivano-Frankivsk Region
Partner Organization(s)	These projects are co-financed by the Interreg VI-A NEXT Romania–Ukraine Program 2021–2027.
Background and Context	<p>Environmental crime and biodiversity degradation represent shared challenges in the Romanian–Ukrainian cross-border region, particularly in forested and mountainous protected areas where ecosystems extend across national boundaries. Activities such as poaching, illegal logging, and habitat degradation can easily cross borders, while differences in legal frameworks, operational procedures, and institutional mandates often limit the effectiveness of isolated national responses.</p> <p>Within this context, the Interreg VI-A NEXT Romania–Ukraine Program 2021–2027 provides a structured financial and institutional framework to support cross-border cooperation aimed at strengthening environmental protection and biodiversity conservation. The program enables joint initiatives that enhance institutional capacity, promote coordination between authorities, and support practical, field-based cooperation mechanisms.</p> <p>This good practice is implemented through two complementary Interreg projects: “Increase cross-border cooperation and operational capacity of partner structures for a better conservation of biodiversity and of the protected areas” and “Improved guarding and intervention in Maramureş and Ivano-Frankivsk natural protected areas.” Both projects were designed to address common environmental challenges by combining strategic coordination with operational cooperation in protected areas located along the Romanian–Ukrainian border.</p> <p>The cooperation involves law-enforcement structures from both countries, including the Satu Mare County Gendarmerie Inspectorate and the Maramureş County Gendarmerie Inspectorate in Romania, together with units of the National Guard of Ukraine operating in the Zakarpattia and Ivano-Frankivsk regions. By jointly focusing on surveillance, control, conservation, and protection of biodiversity in shared mountain and forest ecosystems, the projects provide a coordinated operational response to environmental crime affecting cross-border protected areas.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice centers on the design and implementation of joint cross-border operational exercises as a tool to strengthen law enforcement cooperation for biodiversity and forest protection.</p> <p>The approach combines preparatory coordination with hands-on operational testing through the following components:</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Joint Operational Planning and Guidelines: Romanian and Ukrainian partners jointly analyzed trends in environmental crime and developed common guidelines on methods and procedures for combating biodiversity-related offenses. These guidelines provided a shared operational framework to be applied during joint field activities. 2. Joint Operational Exercises: A core element of the cooperation was the organization of joint operational exercises, designed to simulate real-life scenarios related to forest surveillance, environmental crime detection, and intervention in protected areas. These exercises allowed personnel from both countries to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Apply jointly developed guidelines in practice. • Test coordination mechanisms and command structures. • Familiarize themselves with each other’s operational procedures. • Use newly acquired equipment in realistic field conditions. 3. Operational Capacity Building: The exercises were supported by targeted investments in equipment and mobility, improving response time and operational effectiveness in remote and difficult terrain. This ensured that joint actions could be carried out under comparable technical conditions.
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Successful implementation of joint cross-border operational exercises. • Improved coordination and interoperability between Romanian and Ukrainian law enforcement units. • Practical testing and validation of joint guidelines and procedures. • Enhanced readiness to respond to environmental crimes in protected areas. • Strengthened professional networks between field-level enforcement personnel.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong support from the Interreg VI-A NEXT Romania–Ukraine Program. • Clear operational focus on practical, field-based cooperation. • Joint development of guidelines prior to exercises. • Investment in compatible equipment and mobility solutions. • Institutional commitment from both law enforcement partners.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://keep.eu/projects/31206/Improved-guarding-and-inter-EN/

3.4. Coordinated cross-border enforcement to prevent poaching and biodiversity crime in the Danube River

Country / Region Involved	Danube River cross-border region Romania – Bulgaria
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police Giurgiu (Romania)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Giurgiu County Gendarmerie Inspectorate (Romania) • Giurgiu County Police Inspectorate (Romania) • Executive Agency for Fisheries and Aquaculture (Bulgaria) • Environmental and fisheries control authorities
Background and Context	<p>The Danube River basin hosts extensive protected areas and Natura 2000 sites shared by Romania and Bulgaria. For many years, this region has been affected by illegal fishing, poaching, and other environmental crimes, causing ecological damage and undermining biodiversity conservation efforts.</p> <p>The transboundary nature of these activities, combined with outdated equipment and fragmented enforcement capacities, limited the effectiveness of isolated national actions. This situation highlighted the need for coordinated cross-border enforcement, improved operational capacity, and shared intervention frameworks to protect the Danube ecosystem.</p> <p>Within this context, the BioGuard project, funded under the Interreg VI-A Romania–Bulgaria Program, established a structured framework for joint law enforcement cooperation targeting environmental crime in the cross-border river area.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>Good practice is based on integrated cross-border enforcement mechanisms combining strategic coordination, operational cooperation, infrastructure investment, and capacity building.</p> <p>Joint Enforcement Framework</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and signing of a cross-border cooperation agreement focused on biodiversity protection and prevention of illegal activities. • Elaboration of joint strategies and joint action plans addressing poaching, illegal fishing, and environmental crime affecting the Danube ecosystem. <p>Operational Coordination and Infrastructure</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a Zonal Operational Center (ZOC) in Giurgiu County, designed to serve as: a coordination hub for joint enforcement actions; a training facility for enforcement personnel, and a storage site for confiscated goods from enforcement operations in both countries. <p>Capacity Building and Equipment</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Procurement of specialized surveillance and intervention equipment, including thermal imaging binoculars, night vision devices, and operational vehicles. • Joint training activities in border management and environmental enforcement, improving interoperability between police, border guards, gendarmerie, and fisheries authorities. <p>Joint Operations and Exercises</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning and implementation of joint field exercises and coordinated controls along the Danube River. • Alignment of intervention tactics and procedures for detecting and responding to environmental crimes. <p>Public Awareness and Prevention</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of cross-border awareness campaigns on biodiversity protection and the impacts of illegal activities. • Communication activities supporting prevention and community engagement alongside enforcement actions.
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a permanent cross-border enforcement framework targeting environmental crime. • Improved intervention capacity of law enforcement and environmental authorities on both sides of the border. • Enhanced coordination and information exchange between police, border guards, gendarmerie, and fisheries authorities. • Creation of shared infrastructure supporting long-term cooperation beyond the project duration.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong institutional cooperation between law enforcement and environmental authorities. • Integration of strategic planning, operational capacity, and training within a single framework. • Investment in shared infrastructure and equipment supporting joint enforcement. • Use of EU territorial cooperation funding to address structural capacity gaps.
Challenges and Lessons Learned	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Differences in administrative procedures required continuous coordination. • Procurement and infrastructure development involved complex timelines. • Sustained cooperation requires long-term commitment beyond project funding.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://interregviarobg.eu/en/interreg-projects/ROBG00018 • https://keep.eu/projects/30199/Safeguarding-biodiversity-a-EN/

3.5. Strengthening cross-border law-enforcement capacity for biodiversity protection in the Bihor–Hajdú-Bihar Euroregion

Country / Region Involved	Bihor County and Hajdú-Bihar County Euroregion Romania – Hungary
Lead Organization(s)	Bihor County Gendarmerie Inspectorate (Romania)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Hajdú-Bihar County Development Agency (Hungary), managed by the Hajdú-Bihar County Council
Background and Context	<p>The Bihor–Hajdú-Bihar Euroregion is a shared cross-border area between Romania and Hungary that hosts valuable natural ecosystems, including protected areas, forests, wetlands, and sites belonging to the Natura 2000 network. These ecosystems provide essential services for biodiversity conservation, climate resilience, and local communities.</p> <p>At the same time, the region faces increasing environmental pressures caused by illegal fishing, poaching, habitat destruction, and other forms of environmental crime. These activities often extend across national borders, limiting the effectiveness of actions carried out solely at the national or local level. Differences in institutional responsibilities, operational practices, and awareness among stakeholders further complicate coordinated responses.</p> <p>Within this context, the Interreg VI-A Romania–Hungary Program 2021–2027 provides a structured framework to support cross-border cooperation for a greener and more resilient border area. The program enables joint initiatives that combine institutional cooperation, capacity building, and public awareness to address shared environmental challenges.</p> <p>The project “Improving cross-border capacity for conservation and protection of nature, biodiversity, green and blue infrastructure in the Bihor–Hajdú-Bihar Euroregion” was developed to respond to these challenges by promoting coordinated law-enforcement action, joint planning, and increased public engagement in biodiversity protection.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice is based on an integrated cross-border cooperation model combining joint planning, awareness raising, and capacity building to improve the protection of biodiversity and natural resources in the Bihor–Hajdú-Bihar Euroregion. A core activity is the development of a Joint Action Plan, agreed upon by both Romanian and Hungarian partners for the first time. The plan establishes common priorities, roles, and procedures for the surveillance, control, conservation, and protection of ecosystems and forestry in the cross-border area.</p> <p>To support this process, the partners organize joint workshops on both sides of the border, bringing together law-enforcement authorities, decision-makers, environmental stakeholders, and sectoral actors. These workshops focus on identifying emerging trends in environmental crime, defining shared risks, and developing common methods and procedures for biodiversity protection.</p> <p>The project places strong emphasis on public awareness and stakeholder engagement. A series of awareness and information events are organized in both countries, targeting decision-makers, industry representatives, local communities, and schools.</p>

	<p>These activities aim to increase understanding of biodiversity conservation, responsible environmental behavior, and the consequences of environmental crime. In parallel, the operational capacity of partner institutions is strengthened through the provision of specialized equipment, including 4x4 off-road vehicles, thermal imaging drones, surveillance cameras, and other monitoring tools. This equipment improves the ability of authorities to operate in difficult terrain and respond more effectively to illegal activities affecting protected areas.</p>
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and adoption of a Joint Action Plan for biodiversity protection in the Euroregion. • Improved coordination between Romanian and Hungarian institutions responsible for environmental protection. • Increased awareness among decision-makers, industry actors, and local communities. • Enhanced monitoring, surveillance, and intervention capacity through specialized equipment. • Establishment of a framework for continued cross-border cooperation and upscaling of joint solutions.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong institutional cooperation supported by the Interreg VI-A Romania–Hungary Program. • Clear focus on joint planning as a foundation for coordinated action. • Combination of awareness-raising activities with operational capacity building. • Engagement of both law-enforcement and development-oriented institutions. • Integration of lessons learned from previous cross-border cooperation initiatives.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://keep.eu/projects/31482/Improving-cross-border-capacity-EN/

4. BEST PRACTICES LED BY NON-STATE ACTORS

Civil society- and research-driven approaches to
transboundary prevention and enforcement of
pollution and wildlife crime

4.1. Integrated environmental crime enforcement and intelligence model for biodiversity protection

Country / Region Involved	Spain and Portugal with outreach and replication potential across other EU Member States
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sociedad Española de Ornitología (SEO/BirdLife) – Spain
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Sociedade Portuguesa para o Estudo das Aves (SPEA) – Portugal Consejería de Medio Ambiente y Ordenación del Territorio, Junta de Andalucía – Spain. Servicio de Protección de la Naturaleza (SEPRONA), Guardia Civil – Spain Funded under the EU LIFE Program (Project reference: LIFE17 GIE/ES/000630 – LIFE Nature Guardians)
Background and Context	<p>The EU LIFE Program is the Union’s main financial instrument supporting environmental and climate action. LIFE projects play a key role in improving the implementation and enforcement of EU environmental law, strengthening governance, and promoting cooperation between public authorities, civil society organizations, and enforcement bodies.</p> <p>Within this framework, LIFE Nature Guardians was designed to address structural weaknesses in environmental crime enforcement by introducing an integrated model that combines specialized training, environmental intelligence, advanced investigative tools, legal action, citizen reporting mechanisms, and large-scale awareness-raising. The project responds to the need for a systemic approach that links prevention, detection, prosecution, and social engagement to effectively reduce environmental crime and improve biodiversity protection.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice is built on a multi-layered enforcement and governance model, integrating operational, legal, technical, and social dimensions of environmental crime prevention and prosecution.</p> <p>1. Capacity building and specialized training</p> <p>The project delivered extensive training programs for law enforcement officers, prosecutors, judges, environmental agents, and legal professionals. Over 1,500 enforcement agents across Spain, Portugal, and other EU countries received specialized training on:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigation of biodiversity-related crimes. Environmental cybercrime and online wildlife trafficking. Open-Source Intelligence (OSINT). Financial investigations and tracking of illegal profits. Legal procedures and evidentiary challenges in environmental crime cases. <p>Training materials included the first Police Investigation Manual for biodiversity crimes in the EU, published in Spanish, English, Portuguese, and Greek.</p> <p>2. Environmental intelligence and innovative enforcement tools</p> <p>A core innovation of the project was the establishment of the first Environmental Police Intelligence Unit in the EU, the National Central Office (OCN) within SEPRONA (Guardia Civil). This unit:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralized environmental crime data. • Produced Environmental Intelligence Bulletins (BIMA). • Strengthened coordination between national and regional enforcement units. <p>The project also equipped enforcement bodies with advanced surveillance and investigation tools, including drones, tracking devices, mobile laboratories, and digital forensic equipment.</p> <p>3. Strengthening legal action and reducing impunity LIFE Nature Guardians actively supported judicial proceedings by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Participating in strategic litigation on wildlife crime, habitat destruction, illegal hunting, poisoning, and electrocution of birds. • Developing practical legal guides to address procedural and interpretative challenges in environmental criminal cases. • Supporting the prosecution of over 30 emblematic cases, contributing to jurisprudence that strengthens environmental protection. <p>These actions resulted in a 34.5% increase in judicial proceedings related to wildlife and plant crimes.</p> <p>4. Citizen reporting and data systems The project developed and promoted citizen reporting mechanisms, including a web-based complaints portal, which processed over 1,000 citizen complaints and generated more than 700 formal reports to authorities. In parallel, the project contributed to the creation of SICMA, the Spanish Information System on Captures and Accidental Deaths, providing a standardized methodology for collecting and analyzing data on wildlife mortality caused by illegal activities.</p> <p>5. Awareness raising and social engagement Large-scale awareness campaigns were implemented to change public perception of environmental crime. Key actions included:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A permanent exhibition at the National Museum of Natural Sciences on the constitutional right to a healthy environment (visited by over 300,000 people). • Public murals addressing wildlife crime in high-risk areas. • Educational programs for schools and communities. • Media campaigns and symbolic actions, such as displaying the environmental rights flag aboard the Spanish Navy training ship.
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 110% increase in detection of environmental crimes in Spain. • 87% increase in detections in Portugal. • 62% reduction in wildlife mortality caused by illegal activities since project launch. • 34.5% increase in judicial proceedings for biodiversity-related crimes. • Establishment of the EU's first environmental police intelligence unit. • Training of over 1,500 enforcement agents and more than 1,000 legal and technical professionals. • Creation of harmonized tools for data collection, investigation, and economic valuation of wildlife damage. • Measurable increase in public awareness and trust in environmental enforcement authorities.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated approach linking intelligence, enforcement, legal action, and public engagement. • Strong cooperation between NGOs, law enforcement agencies, and public authorities.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Use of environmental intelligence and innovative investigative technologies. • Combination of preventive, repressive, and educational measures. • High level of institutional commitment and long-term sustainability of results.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://guardianes.seo.org/ • https://guardianes.seo.org/download/manual-de-investigacion-policial-de-delitos-e-infracciones-contra-la-biodiversidad/ • https://guardianes.seo.org/download/lecciones-practicas-aprendidas-sobre-actuacion-legal-en-procedimientos-penales-por-delitos-ambientales/ • https://guardianes.seo.org/download/estudio-sobre-el-origen-y-las-motivaciones-de-la-criminalidad-ambiental/ • https://guardianes.seo.org/download/estudio-sobre-el-caracter-disuasorio-efectivo-y-proporcional-de-las-sanciones-penales-impuestas-en-espana-y-portugal-en-delitos-contra-el-medio-ambiente-y-su-adequacion-a-la-directiva-2008-99-ec-sob-2/

4.2. Building capacity and cooperation to combat illegal bird crime along European migratory flyways

Country / Region Involved	European Union and neighboring Mediterranean flyway countries with a focus on Cyprus, Croatia, Greece, and Italy
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Stichting BirdLife Europe (Netherlands)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> National BirdLife partner organizations and civil society groups in priority flyway countries Law enforcement authorities, customs services, and environmental inspectorates Judicial authorities and prosecutors Volunteer ranger networks and conservation NGOs Supported under the EU LIFE Program (Project reference: LIFE17 GIE/NL/000599)
Background and Context	<p>Illegal killing, trapping, and trade of birds (IKB) remains one of the most widespread wildlife crimes in Europe and the Mediterranean region, particularly along major migratory flyways. Millions of birds are affected annually by practices such as illegal hunting, trapping with mist nets or lime sticks, and the use of electronic calling devices. These activities undermine the objectives of the EU Birds Directive and pose a direct threat to migratory species protected at EU level.</p> <p>The challenge is inherently transboundary. Many bird species migrate across several countries during their annual life cycle, meaning that illegal activities in one country can have direct impacts on biodiversity in others. Enforcement gaps, uneven political commitment, limited capacity of authorities, and low public awareness have historically reduced the effectiveness of national responses.</p> <p>The LIFE Program is the European Union's dedicated funding instrument for environment and climate action. LIFE projects support the implementation of EU environmental legislation, strengthen governance and enforcement, and promote cooperation between public authorities, civil society, and stakeholders. Within this framework, the project LIFE Against Bird Crime addressed a critical enforcement and governance gap: the need for coordinated, flyway-scale action combining awareness-raising, enforcement support, monitoring, and policy advocacy.</p> <p>LIFE Against Bird Crime was designed to support the delivery of the EU Biodiversity Strategy and the Birds Directive by reducing illegal bird killing through a mix of practical field actions, capacity building, volunteer engagement, and cross-border cooperation in priority flyway countries.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice is based on an integrated, multi-level approach to combating bird crime across borders, combining enforcement support, civil society engagement, and policy action.</p> <p>1. Cross-border monitoring and data collection The project expanded and improved knowledge on illegal bird killing by supporting systematic monitoring across priority countries. Innovative tools were introduced, including Acoustic Recording Units (ARUs) to detect illegal shooting activity, enabling evidence-based assessment of poaching intensity, particularly in Greece.</p> <p>2. Support to enforcement and joint field actions LIFE Against Bird Crime strengthened cooperation between NGOs, volunteer ranger networks, and enforcement authorities. Joint patrols, inspections, and targeted operations were carried out, including:</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coordinated enforcement actions against illegal electronic bird calls in Italy. • Removal of poaching infrastructure (e.g. hides) in protected Natura 2000 sites in Croatia. • Support to police raids targeting illegal bird markets in Greece. <p>3. Volunteer engagement and capacity building The project mobilized and trained volunteers to support monitoring, reporting, and awareness-raising. Volunteers played a key role in detecting illegal activities and supporting enforcement bodies, increasing coverage in remote or high-risk areas.</p> <p>4. Awareness raising and public engagement Large-scale communication campaigns, including the “Flight for Survival” campaign, reached millions of citizens across Europe. Educational activities targeted schools, local communities, hunters, and decision-makers to change social norms around bird crime.</p> <p>5. Policy advocacy and strategic planning The project actively supported national and international policy processes, contributing to the Rome Strategic Plan (2020–2030), which commits governments to achieving at least a 50% reduction in illegal bird killing by 2030. Partners engaged in continuous dialogue with authorities to improve legislation, enforcement priorities, and resource allocation.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First-time use of acoustic monitoring technology for detecting illegal hunting in Greece. • Successful joint enforcement operations, including over 680 inspections and dozens of criminal cases in Italy. • Increased confiscation and release of illegally traded birds in Greece. • Strengthened volunteer ranger networks supporting enforcement. • Adoption and implementation of Local Action Plans against bird crime in Greece. • Contribution to flyway-level strategic planning through the Rome Strategic Plan.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Flyway-based approach addressing the full migratory cycle of birds. • Strong cooperation between NGOs, volunteers, and enforcement authorities. • Combination of enforcement support and public awareness measures. • Use of innovative monitoring tools to support evidence-based action.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://flightforsurvival.org/download-documents/ • https://flightforsurvival.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/LABC-FINAL-Report-31012023.pdf • https://flightforsurvival.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/05/LIFE-B3-Policy-Recommendation-Report.pdf • https://flightforsurvival.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/Guidelines-for-IKB-monitoring_UPDATED_2022.pdf

4.3. SWiPE project: strengthening wildlife crime prosecution through evidence, capacity building and cross-border cooperation in Europe

Country / Region Involved	11 European countries , including EU Member States, EU candidate countries, and potential EU candidate countries Bulgaria, Croatia, Romania, Serbia, Spain, Hungary, Italy, Poland, Slovakia, Ukraine, and additional associated countries through project networks.
Lead Organization(s)	WWF Bulgaria (Lead Partner of the LIFE SWiPE Project)
Partner Organization(s)	The SWiPE consortium comprises 13 partners from 11 countries, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • State Attorney’s Office of the Republic of Croatia • Judicial Academy Croatia • Fauna & Flora International (Romania) • WWF Adria (Croatia and Serbia) • WWF Spain • WWF Hungary & TRAFFIC • WWF Italy • WWF Poland • WWF Romania • WWF Slovakia • WWF Ukraine The project was funded by the EU LIFE Program, with additional national co-financing in several countries. Project Reference: LIFE19 GIE/BG/000846
Background and Context	Wildlife crime in Europe—including poaching, illegal killing, poisoning, illegal trade, and persecution of protected species—remains a significant threat to biodiversity despite the existence of extensive international, European Union (EU), and national legislation. Legal instruments such as the EU Birds Directive, Habitats Directive, the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora (CITES), and national criminal laws formally prohibit these activities. However, experience across Member States has shown that the main challenge lies not in the absence of legal frameworks, but in their uneven enforcement and prosecution. The LIFE SWiPE project was implemented within the framework of the EU LIFE Program, the European Union’s dedicated funding instrument for environment, nature conservation, biodiversity, and climate action. Since its launch in 1992, the LIFE Program has supported pilot, demonstration, and capacity-building projects that improve the implementation of EU environmental and climate policy. LIFE projects often act as testing grounds for innovative approaches, foster cooperation between public authorities and civil society, and help bridge the gap between EU legislation and on-the-ground implementation. Wildlife crimes are frequently perceived as a low-priority offence within national justice systems. Investigations are often incomplete, cases discontinued before reaching court, or sanctions applied inconsistently and without sufficient deterrent effect. Prosecutors and judges faced multiple structural barriers, including limited access to reliable and comparable wildlife crime data, insufficient specialized training, fragmented institutional responsibilities, and weak coordination between enforcement agencies. As a result, wildlife crime often combined high economic profit with low prosecution, making it attractive to organized criminal networks.

	<p>A key gap identified by the project was the lack of robust and harmonized evidence based on wildlife crime across Europe. Information on investigations, prosecutions, and judicial outcomes was scattered among institutions, rarely standardized, and seldom analyzed in a systematic way. This hindered prosecutors' ability to build strong cases, limited opportunities for cross-border cooperation, and reduced policymakers' capacity to evaluate enforcement effectiveness or identify priority crime trends.</p> <p>At the same time, wildlife crime increasingly operates across borders, involving shared species populations, transnational trafficking routes, and organized networks active in multiple countries. While criminal activities transcend national boundaries, prosecution and judicial cooperation mechanisms have often remained nationally fragmented, with few structured platforms for sustained knowledge exchange and collaboration among prosecutors and enforcement authorities.</p> <p>In this context, the LIFE SWiPE (Successful Wildlife Crime Prosecution in Europe) project was designed as a targeted intervention to strengthen the prosecution and judicial response to wildlife crime. The project brought together a consortium of 13 partners from 11 European countries, including environmental authorities, prosecution bodies, judicial training institutions, and non-governmental organizations. Its focus was on reinforcing the entire prosecution chain—from data collection and case preparation to court proceedings and sanctioning—while promoting cross-border cooperation and shared learning.</p> <p>By aligning with EU priorities such as the EU Action Plan against Wildlife Trafficking, the Environmental Compliance Assurance framework, and the recognition of environmental crime as a priority area in the fight against serious and organized crime, LIFE SWiPE aimed to reduce impunity, increase deterrence, and contribute to the long-term conservation of Europe's biodiversity through more effective and consistent wildlife crime prosecution.</p>
<p>Description of Activities / Actions Implemented</p>	<p>This good practice consists of an integrated European model for improving wildlife crime prosecution, combining data collection, professional training, institutional cooperation, and public communication.</p> <p>Key components include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Systematic data collection and analysis of wildlife crime cases in 11 countries, identifying investigation gaps, prosecution barriers, and sanctioning practices. • Capacity building for prosecutors and enforcement authorities, focusing on legal interpretation, evidence handling, and cross-border case cooperation. • Structured cross-border knowledge exchange, enabling prosecutors and investigators to share experiences, case law, and investigative strategies. • Establishment of a permanent information-sharing platform, facilitating access to wildlife crime resources, guidance, and case examples. • Public communication of successful prosecutions, aimed at reducing the perception of impunity and strengthening deterrence. <p>The approach integrates legal, institutional, and operational perspectives and actively involves both public authorities and NGOs, ensuring a comprehensive response to wildlife crime.</p> <p>Established cooperation mechanisms</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal cooperation between prosecutors, police, customs, and environmental authorities across 11 countries. • Cross-border professional networks linking prosecution and investigation chains. • Joint training activities and workshops involving prosecutors, judges, and enforcement officers.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaboration between NGOs and public authorities in data collection, case analysis, and advocacy. • Long-term cooperation ensured through post-project continuation of platforms and networks.
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The project produced the most comprehensive and structured collection of wildlife crime (WLC) data in Europe to date, applying a common methodology across participating countries. This significantly improved data comparability and reliability at both national and European levels. • LIFE SWiPE developed national wildlife crime baseline reports for 11 European countries, covering a five-year period (2016–2020). These reports provided, for the first time, a consolidated overview of investigation, prosecution, and sanctioning practices in both EU Member States and non-EU countries. • The project addressed major knowledge gaps regarding the scale, patterns, and prosecution outcomes of wildlife crime in Europe, creating a solid evidence base to inform institutional capacity-building and the design of targeted training programs for prosecutors and enforcement • Creation of the European wildlife crime information portal (https://stopwildlifecrime.eu), maintained for at least five years post-project • 896 experts trained, including 283 prosecutors.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong leadership by an experienced environmental NGO with extensive European networks. • Direct involvement of prosecutors and judicial institutions from the outset. • Combination of technical training, practical case analysis, and policy advocacy. • Cross-border scope addressing transnational nature of wildlife crime. • Integration of NGOs as facilitators between enforcement, prosecution, and policy levels. • Long-term sustainability ensured through after-LIFE strategies and continued network operation.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE19-GIE-BG-000846/successful-wildlife-crime-prosecution-in-europe • https://stopwildlifecrime.eu/

4.4. Cross-border environmental monitoring of the Danube River using integrated aerial, river-based, and renewable-energy systems

Country / Region Involved	Danube River corridor in the Ruse, Giurgiu, Silistra and Călărași regions Romania – Bulgaria
Lead Organization(s)	University of Ruse “Angel Kanchev” (Bulgaria)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICPE-CA – National Institute for R&D in Electrical Engineering (Romania) COMOTI – National Research and Development Institute for Gas Turbines (Romania)
Background and Context	<p>The Danube River is Europe’s second longest river and a critical natural asset for millions of people, industries, and ecosystems across ten countries. Along the Romanian–Bulgarian border, the river supports wetlands, protected areas, and biodiversity hotspots designated under international frameworks such as UNESCO and Natura 2000. At the same time, this shared ecosystem faces increasing pressure from pollution, industrial and agricultural activities, habitat degradation, and the growing impacts of climate change.</p> <p>Environmental threats affecting the Danube do not respect national borders. Pollution introduced in one section of the river can quickly affect downstream ecosystems and communities in another country. Despite this interdependence, environmental monitoring has traditionally been fragmented, relying on national systems, limited spatial coverage, and delayed data availability. This has constrained the ability of authorities and stakeholders to respond rapidly and effectively to emerging environmental risks.</p> <p>Within this context, the Interreg VI-A Romania–Bulgaria Program 2021–2027 provides a structured framework for cross-border cooperation aimed, between others, at enhancing environmental protection, biodiversity conservation, and pollution reduction. The program supports joint initiatives that combine scientific expertise, technological innovation, and institutional cooperation.</p> <p>The Danube River Environmental Assessment and Monitoring (DREAM) Project was developed as a response to these challenges. It introduces an integrated, technology-based monitoring approach designed to generate accurate, real-time environmental data and support evidence-based decision-making. The pilot system would be implemented along the Silistra–Călărași and Ruse–Giurgiu section of the Danube, covering the river and both banks within a radius of approximately 3–5 kilometers, including wetlands, nature reserves, and protected areas of high ecological value.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice focuses on the joint development and deployment of an advanced Environmental Factors Monitoring System (EFMS) for the cross-border section of the Danube River. The EFMS is designed to function as an early warning and decision-support system, enabling continuous observation of environmental conditions and rapid detection of pollution or ecosystem degradation.</p> <p>The system integrates several complementary monitoring tools:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), also known as drones, equipped with sensors for air quality measurement, visual inspection, noise monitoring, and terrain mapping. These UAVs enable rapid and flexible coverage of large river sections and surrounding areas.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Air and water quality sensors, installed on mobile and fixed platforms, to measure key indicators such as pollution levels, temperature, and other environmental parameters relevant to ecosystem health. • A solar-powered river vessel, which serves as a mobile monitoring platform for water quality assessment. Powered by renewable energy, the vessel supports long-term monitoring while minimizing environmental impact. • A digital data platform, which collects, processes, and stores monitoring data in real time. This platform enables access for public authorities, researchers, and the public, supporting transparency and shared understanding of environmental conditions. <p>The partners jointly designed the system architecture, assessed operational risks, and coordinated procurement to ensure compatibility and sustainability of all components. In parallel, the project promotes cross-border collaboration and stakeholder engagement through workshops, surveys, public events, and an open-access website. These activities aim to raise awareness among local communities, industries, and decision-makers about environmental risks, conservation needs, and pollution reduction measures.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a cross-border Environmental Factors Monitoring System covering multiple sections of the Danube River. • Improved availability of reliable, real-time data on water quality, air pollution, and environmental conditions. • Use of renewable energy solutions to support long-term monitoring activities. • Strengthened cooperation between Bulgarian and Romanian research and technical institutions. • Increased transparency through public access to environmental data.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong financial and institutional support from the Interreg VI-A Romania-Bulgaria Program. • Clear definition of roles among partners with complementary scientific and technical expertise. • Integration of innovative monitoring technologies with sustainable energy solutions. • Early involvement of stakeholders and the public through open data and communication activities.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://dreamproject.eco/ • https://interregviarobg.eu/en/interreg-projects/ROBG00169 • https://keep.eu/projects/30193/Danube-River-Environmental--EN/

5. BEST PRACTICES LED BY TRANSBOUNDARY AND EUROPEAN COOPERATION NETWORKS

Network-based approaches to transboundary
prevention and enforcement of pollution and wildlife
crime

5.1. TransParcNet Annual Meetings

European network for cooperation and knowledge exchange among transboundary protected areas

Country / Region Involved	About 13 European countries that are members of the Transboundary Parks Network
Lead Organization(s)	EUROPARC Federation (through the Transboundary Parks Program / TransParcNet)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management authorities of EUROPARC-certified Transboundary Parks • Protected area authorities from participant member states • Experts from biodiversity conservation authorities and research institutions
Background and Context	<p>In 2003, the EUROPARC Federation launched the Transboundary Parks Program during the 5th World Parks Congress, establishing a framework to support cooperation between protected areas located in or adjacent to international borders. The program introduced the Basic Standards for Transboundary Cooperation, accompanied by a verification and certification process for participant protected areas.</p> <p>As part of this program, TransParcNet was established as a network connecting all protected areas certified under the EUROPARC Transboundary Parks Program. The network organizes annual TransParcNet Meetings, hosted each year in a different transboundary protected area in Europe. These meetings bring together representatives of certified transboundary parks, candidate areas, and relevant experts to exchange information on cross-border management practices.</p> <p>Since its creation, TransParcNet has functioned as a regular platform for information exchange and coordination among transboundary protected areas participating in the EUROPARC framework.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>The TransParcNet Annual Meeting is organized every year in a different EUROPARC Transboundary Area, ensuring broad geographic representation and exposure to diverse management contexts. The meeting typically spans several days and combines structured discussion with experiential learning.</p> <p>Key activities include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thematic conferences and workshops focusing on transboundary biodiversity conservation, governance, ecosystem management, and sustainable regional development. • Exchange of experiences and know-how, allowing participants to share successes, challenges, and innovative solutions from their respective transboundary areas. • Field excursions and site visits, offering first-hand insight into local conservation practices, governance models, and cross-border initiatives. • Networking and peer learning, strengthening trust and long-term cooperation among protected area professionals across Europe.
Results and Achievements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Creation of a strong and cohesive European network of transboundary protected area managers and experts. • Improved coordination and alignment of management approaches across borders.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development and dissemination of concrete outputs, such as the Practical Guidelines for Transboundary Protected Area Managers in Europe, based on case studies and best practices from certified areas.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A clear and shared framework provided by the EUROPARC Transboundary Parks Program and its Basic Standards for Transboundary Cooperation. • Regular, face-to-face interaction through annual meetings hosted in different transboundary regions. • Combination of strategic discussions and practical field-based learning. • A robust verification and certification system, ensuring quality, credibility, and continuous improvement. • Strong sense of community and trust among participating authorities.
Transferability / Replicability	It can be replicated by involving those transboundary parks who do not participate or are not certified yet.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.euoparc.org/transboundary-parks-programme/transparcnet/ • https://www.euoparc.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Practical-Guidelines-for-TBA-Managers-2024-1.pdf • https://www.euoparc.org/transboundary-parks-programme/

5.2. European Network of Environmental Prosecutors (ENPE): strengthening cross-border prosecution of environmental crime

Country / Region Involved	European Union (EU Member States)
Lead Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environment Agency (United Kingdom)
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment (EUFJE) • National prosecution authorities and judicial bodies across EU Member States • Associated international partners and networks (e.g. Interpol, UNEP-linked initiatives) • Supported under the EU LIFE Program (LIFE14 GIE/UK/000043)
Background and Context	<p>Environmental crime, including illegal waste shipments, wildlife trafficking, and air-pollution offences represent one of the most profitable forms of organized crime globally, with serious consequences for biodiversity, human health, and economic stability. These crimes frequently cross-national borders, exploit legal and institutional differences between countries, and require complex technical and legal expertise to investigate and prosecute effectively. Despite a strong body of EU environmental legislation, enforcement and prosecution outcomes have historically been uneven across Member States, limiting deterrence and undermining the credibility of environmental law.</p> <p>The LIFE Program is the European Union’s dedicated funding instrument for environmental, climate, and nature protection. LIFE projects are designed to pilot innovative solutions, improve implementation of EU legislation, build institutional capacity, and facilitate cooperation across borders. Unlike traditional infrastructure funding, LIFE projects focus strongly on governance, enforcement, knowledge transfer, and long-term systemic change.</p> <p>Within this framework, the LIFE-ENPE project (European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment) addressed a critical enforcement gap: the lack of structured, permanent cooperation between prosecutors and judges responsible for environmental crime across Europe. Before LIFE-ENPE, no formal European-level network existed to support prosecutors in sharing case experience, aligning legal interpretations, or cooperating on transnational environmental cases.</p> <p>LIFE-ENPE responded to this need by creating a self-sustaining transnational network of environmental prosecutors and judges, supported by targeted training, thematic working groups, and practical guidance tools. The project focused on strengthening prosecution capacity for complex crimes, particularly waste crime, wildlife crime, and air pollution, while also promoting consistent sanctioning and better implementation of EU environmental law.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>This good practice is based on the establishment and operation of the European Network of Environmental Prosecutors (ENPE) as a structured mechanism for cross-border cooperation, knowledge exchange, and capacity building in environmental crime prosecution.</p> <p>1. Establishment of a Transnational Prosecutorial Network</p> <p>LIFE-ENPE created the first dedicated European network of prosecutors specializing in environmental crime. The network provided an institutional framework for regular</p>

	<p>cooperation, replacing ad hoc and informal contacts with a structured and durable system.</p> <p>2. Thematic Working Groups Four permanent Working Groups were established to address priority areas of environmental crime:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Waste crime. • Wildlife crime. • Air pollution crime. • Legislative and policy alignment. <p>Each Working Group produced guidance documents, analytical reports, and recommendations aimed at improving investigation techniques, prosecution strategies, and legal interpretation across jurisdictions.</p> <p>3. Training and Capacity Building The project delivered targeted training activities for prosecutors and judges, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case-based training modules. • Workshops and seminars at national and EU level. • Training materials on prosecution, adjudication, and sanctioning of environmental crime. <p>These activities addressed both legal and technical aspects of environmental crime, improving consistency and quality of prosecutions.</p> <p>4. Information Sharing and Best Practice Exchange ENPE facilitated the systematic exchange of information through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annual conferences. • Regular newsletters. • Online dissemination of guidance, case law examples, and tools. <p>This improved access to expertise and supported mutual learning between Member States.</p> <p>5. Support for EU Environmental Governance ENPE directly supported EU enforcement initiatives, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Environmental Crime Directive. • The Environmental Compliance Assurance initiative. • The EU Environmental Compliance and Governance Forum. <p>The network also contributed to policy discussions and legislative evaluations related to waste shipment, wildlife protection, and pollution control.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a self-sustaining European network of environmental prosecutors. • Network expanded to 41 member organizations by project closure. • Four annual international conferences held, with over 550 legal professionals participating. • Training delivered to prosecutors and judges across 20 countries. • Outreach activities engaging 1,000–1,100 legal and technical professionals. • Improved consistency in legal interpretation and prosecution practices across Member States. • Strengthened cooperation beyond the EU, including links with networks in Latin America, Africa, and Asia.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear focus on prosecutors and judges as key actors in environmental enforcement.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutionalized cooperation replacing informal personal networks. • Thematic Working Groups addressing concrete crime categories. • Combination of legal, technical, and policy expertise. • Long-term sustainability ensured through a framework partnership agreement.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.environmentalprosecutors.eu/ • https://www.environmentalprosecutors.eu/eu-life-project • https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE14-GIE-UK-000043/european-network-of-prosecutors-for-the-environment

5.3. IMPEL: European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law

Country / Region Involved	<p>IMPEL involves environmental authorities from 38 countries, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All EU Member States • EEA and EFTA countries (e.g. Norway, Iceland, Switzerland) • EU candidate and potential candidate countries, such as North Macedonia, Serbia, Turkey, Albania, Montenegro and Kosovo
Lead Organization(s)	<p>European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law (IMPEL) International non-profit association under Belgian law</p>
Partner Organization(s)	<p>National and regional environmental authorities of IMPEL member countries In addition, IMPEL works in close cooperation with strategic partner networks and institutions, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission • European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment (ENPE) • EU Forum of Judges for the Environment (EUFJE)
Background and Context	<p>The effective implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation remain a persistent challenge across Europe. While the European Union has developed an extensive body of environmental law, differences in administrative capacity, inspection practices, enforcement priorities, and legal interpretation among countries often result in uneven application on the ground. These gaps can undermine environmental protection, distort fair competition, and weaken public trust in environmental governance.</p> <p>To address these challenges, the European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law (IMPEL) was established in 1992 as an informal cooperation platform among environmental authorities. In 2008, it became an international non-profit association under Belgian law, with its legal seat in Brussels. Today, IMPEL brings together 59 environmental authorities from 38 countries, including all EU Member States, EEA and EFTA countries, EU candidate and potential candidate countries.</p> <p>IMPEL operates within the broader EU environmental governance framework and is explicitly recognized in key EU policy and legislative documents. On 15 September 2009, IMPEL and the European Commission signed a Memorandum of Understanding that formally acknowledged IMPEL’s role in strengthening the implementation and enforcement of EU environmental legislation and set out the framework for cooperation between the two parties. Since then, the European Commission has continued to play a key supporting role, including providing financial support to IMPEL. From 2008 onwards, this support has been channeled through the LIFE+ program.</p>
Description of Activities / Actions Implemented	<p>IMPEL represents a structured, peer-driven cooperation model that enhances the practical implementation and enforcement of EU environmental law through collaboration among national and regional environmental authorities.</p> <p>The core of IMPEL’s work is organized around project-based activities, each governed by clear Terms of Reference (ToR) that define objectives, expected outputs, quality review mechanisms, and dissemination strategies. Projects are jointly managed by environmental authorities from different countries, promoting shared ownership and mutual learning. Key mechanisms implemented by IMPEL include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-to-peer learning and exchange, allowing authorities to share practical experiences, enforcement approaches, and inspection methodologies.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation Review Initiatives (IRIs), which provide structured peer reviews to identify strengths, weaknesses, and opportunities for improvement in national implementation systems. • Development of technical guidance and tools, supporting risk-based inspections, compliance assurance strategies, and effective use of limited enforcement resources. • Cross-border enforcement coordination, particularly in areas such as illegal transboundary waste shipments. • Facilitated cooperation across the compliance chain, connecting inspectors, permitting authorities, prosecutors, judges, ombudsmen, and auditors. • Policy feedback loops, where practical enforcement experience informs EU-level policy development and legislative design. <p>In addition to project work, IMPEL organizes regular international conferences that bring together over 200 experts per event from environmental authorities, the European Commission, industry, and civil society. These conferences serve as platforms for disseminating IMPEL outputs, discussing emerging enforcement challenges, and shaping future work priorities.</p> <p>IMPEL also formalizes cooperation through Memoranda of Understanding (MoUs) with key strategic partners, including the European Commission, ENPE (European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment), EnviCrimeNet, EUFJE (EU Forum of Judges for the Environment), and international conventions such as the Basel, Rotterdam, and Stockholm Conventions.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Established a permanent, self-sustaining European network of environmental authorities dedicated to implementation and enforcement. • Improved consistency and effectiveness of environmental inspections and enforcement practices across member countries. • Enabled faster compliance by facilitating the transfer of tested solutions, methodologies, and good practices. • Strengthened cross-border enforcement cooperation, particularly in complex areas such as illegal waste trafficking. • Produced high-quality guidance documents, tools, and methodologies used by authorities across Europe. • Enhanced policy coherence, ensuring that EU legislation better reflects practical enforcement realities. • Built trust and long-term professional relationships among environmental authorities, contributing to durable cooperation.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peer-based governance model, fostering trust, openness, and mutual learning. • Strong institutional anchoring, with IMPEL members being competent environmental authorities. • Project-driven structure, ensuring concrete outputs and practical relevance. • Formal cooperation agreements with EU institutions and enforcement networks. • Stable financial support, notably through the LIFE Program. • Inclusive participation, involving EU, non-EU, candidate, and EEA countries
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://impel.eu/ • https://impel.eu/contents/files/impel-annual-report-2024-final.pdf

5.4. EUFJE: European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment

<p>Country / Region Involved</p>	<p>EUFJE currently involves members, associated members, honorary members, and observers from more than 40 countries across Europe and beyond, including:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Member States • EEA and EFTA countries (e.g. Norway, Iceland, Switzerland) • EU candidate and potential candidate countries
<p>Lead Organization(s)</p>	<p>European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment (EUFJE) Legal status: International non-profit association under Belgian law EUFJE operates as an independent judicial network, coordinated through its elected Board and General Assembly.</p>
<p>Partner Organization(s)</p>	<p>UFJE works in close and structured cooperation with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission – DG Environment (institutional support and policy dialogue) • United Nations Environment Program (UNEP) • Council of Europe • Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU) (observer participation) <p>Key enforcement and judicial networks:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IMPEL – European Union Network for the Implementation and Enforcement of Environmental Law • ENPE – European Network of Prosecutors for the Environment • EnviCrimeNet – Environmental Crime Network for practitioners
<p>Background and Context</p>	<p>The European Union Forum of Judges for the Environment (EUFJE) is a European, non-profit judicial network that brings together judges and courts with competence or interest in environmental law. It is established as an international non-profit association under Belgian law, with its legal seat in Brussels, and operates independently while maintaining close institutional cooperation with the European Commission, the Council of Europe, and United Nations Environment Program (UNEP).</p> <p>EUFJE was created in 2003 as a direct outcome of global and European recognition of the critical role of the judiciary in ensuring the effectiveness of environmental protection and sustainable development. Its origins can be traced back to the World Summit on Sustainable Development (Johannesburg, 2002), where UNEP convened Presidents of Supreme Courts and Chief Justices worldwide to highlight the responsibility of courts in enforcing environmental law. Following this initiative, regional judicial meetings were organized, and European judges meeting in Rome in 2003 agreed to establish a permanent forum dedicated to environmental adjudication.</p> <p>The Forum was formally constituted by senior members of Europe’s highest courts, including judges from the Cour de Cassation (France), the Corte Suprema di Cassazione (Italy), the Constitutional Court of Belgium, and the Court of Appeal of England and Wales, reflecting its foundation at the highest judicial level. Its inaugural institutional meeting took place at the Court of Justice of the European Union in Luxembourg in 2004, underscoring its European mandate and judicial legitimacy.</p> <p>EUFJE’s membership is composed primarily of judges from administrative, civil and criminal courts at all levels of the judiciary across EU Member States, EFTA countries,</p>

	<p>and former or candidate EU countries. Membership is open to individual judges, courts, and judicial organizations, while candidate countries may participate as observers and third countries as associated members. Representatives of international institutions, including the European Commission, UNEP, and the Council of Europe, participate in an observer capacity. Today, EUFJE includes members, associated members, honorary members, and observers from more than 40 countries, forming one of the most extensive judicial networks dedicated to environmental law worldwide.</p>
<p>Description of Activities / Actions Implemented</p>	<p>This good practice consists of a long-standing, institutionalized judicial network that enhances the effectiveness of environmental law enforcement through training, knowledge exchange, comparative analysis, and cooperation.</p> <p>A core pillar of EUFJE’s work is the organization of annual conferences, usually hosted in the Member State holding the Presidency of the Council of the European Union. Each conference focuses on a pressing theme in environmental laws such as Natura 2000 protection, environmental crime, climate litigation, biodiversity loss, access to justice, or the use of scientific evidence in courts. Prior to each conference, participating judges complete detailed questionnaires, resulting in national reports that provide a unique, comparative overview of how environmental law is implemented and adjudicated across countries. These national contributions are analyzed and synthesized into summary reports, which form the basis for identifying best practices and developing concrete recommendations for national authorities and EU institutions.</p> <p>Beyond conferences, EUFJE actively contributes to capacity building and knowledge production through analytical studies, guidance documents, and judicial tools. An example is the BIOVAL project, jointly developed with IMPEL and ENPE, which provides a non-binding but practical methodology for valuing damage to biodiversity in court proceedings. BIOVAL enables judges and prosecutors to calculate monetary compensation for irreversible harm to wildlife using transparent scientific and legal criteria, thereby strengthening the application of the “polluter pays” principle. The BIOVAL methodology has already been successfully applied and upheld by courts, demonstrating its concrete impact on environmental enforcement.</p> <p>EUFJE is also deeply engaged in European and international policy processes. It actively participates in the implementation of the Aarhus Convention, particularly in the Task Force on Access to Justice, contributes to EU legislative evaluations (such as the Environmental Crime Directive and Environmental Liability Directive), and is regularly consulted by the European Commission’s Directorate-General for Environment. Through its involvement in the Environmental Compliance and Governance Forum, EUFJE helps bridge gaps between law-making, enforcement, and adjudication.</p> <p>Another key strength of EUFJE is its structured cooperation with other enforcement networks, notably IMPEL, ENPE, and EnviCrimeNet. Joint conferences, memoranda of understanding, and coordinated position papers—such as those related to the new Environmental Crime Directive—ensure that judges, prosecutors, inspectors, and police authorities work as an integrated compliance chain. These collaborative efforts promote consistency, mutual understanding, and more effective enforcement of environmental law across borders.</p> <p>Through its sustained focus on judicial training, comparative analysis, practical tools, and institutional cooperation, EUFJE has become a reference platform for strengthening environmental justice in Europe.</p>

<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establishment of a pan-European judicial network involving judges and courts from over 40 countries. • Organization of 20+ annual conferences, generating a unique body of comparative knowledge on EU environmental law enforcement. • Production of national reports and synthesis documents that inform judicial practice and EU policymaking. • Strengthened judicial specialization and improved understanding of complex environmental cases, including biodiversity loss, pollution, climate litigation, and environmental crime. • Direct contribution to EU policy development, including evaluations and revisions of environmental crime, liability, inspection, and access to justice legislation. • Enhanced cross-border cooperation between judges, prosecutors, inspectors, and regulators through joint initiatives with other EU enforcement networks. • Practical impact on case law, including the application of the BIOVAL methodology for ecological damage valuation in courts.
<p>Success factors</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Judicial-led network ensuring credibility, independence, and peer trust. • Long-term institutional support from the European Commission. • Combination of theoretical legal analysis and practical case-based learning. • Strong links with other enforcement actors across the entire compliance chain. • Systematic use of comparative national reporting, enabling mutual learning. • No membership fees, facilitating broad participation.
<p>Supporting Documents or Links</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.eufje.org/index.php?lang=en • https://www.eufje.org/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=66&Itemid=257&lang=en

5.5. EnviCrimeNet: strategic coordination and intelligence framework for combating environmental crime

Country / Region Involved	European Union Member States
Lead Organization(s)	EnviCrimeNet (European Network for Environmental Crime) Legal status: Informal network facilitated by Europol and utilizing existing legal framework
Partner Organization(s)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cooperation with IMPEL, ENPE, and EUFJE • Associated international enforcement networks
Background and Context	<p>The European Network for Environmental Crime (EnviCrimeNet) was established in the early 2010s in response to growing concerns at EU level about the increasing scale, complexity, and profitability of environmental crime, particularly its links to organized criminal networks. In 2011, the Council of the European Union formally welcomed the creation of EnviCrimeNet through Council Resolution 10291/11, recognizing the need for a dedicated strategic forum to strengthen the fight against environmental crime across Member States.</p> <p>From its inception, EnviCrimeNet was conceived as a non-operational, strategic network, bringing together law enforcement authorities, criminal investigation services, and prosecutors with specific expertise in environmental crime. Its primary purpose has been to support Member States in addressing environmental crime at a strategic and policy-oriented level, rather than replacing national operational responsibilities. Through this approach, EnviCrimeNet has progressively evolved into a European center of excellence for criminal matters related to environmental offenses, facilitating the exchange of knowledge, best practices, threat assessments, and strategic intelligence.</p> <p>A defining feature of EnviCrimeNet’s development has been its close institutional link with Europol. Europol has played a central role in supporting the network by acting as its Secretariat, providing logistical, analytical, and coordination support within the existing EU law enforcement cooperation framework. This relationship has enabled EnviCrimeNet to align its strategic outputs with broader EU security priorities.</p> <p>Despite its strategic importance, EnviCrimeNet initially operated as an informal network, which limited its long-term sustainability, governance capacity, and ability to systematically advise EU institutions. The LIFE+ SATEC project (LIFE20 PRE/ES/000001) was designed precisely to address these structural limitations. Funded under the EU LIFE Programme—the European Union’s financial instrument supporting environmental and climate action and the effective implementation of EU environmental law—the project aimed to strengthen EnviCrimeNet’s institutional foundations, consolidate its strategic mandate, and enhance its capacity to contribute to EU-level policymaking.</p> <p>Within this framework, LIFE+ SATEC supported the formal establishment of EnviCrimeNet as a non-profit association, ensuring legal stability and long-term continuity. The project also enhanced EnviCrimeNet’s role in strategic criminal investigation planning, capacity building, and policy advisory processes, particularly</p>

	<p>in relation to emerging environmental crime threats. Importantly, LIFE+ SATEC reinforced coordination with complementary European enforcement and judicial networks—IMPEL (administrative enforcement), ENPE (prosecutors), and EUFJE (judges)—promoting a coherent, multi-actor approach across the entire environmental compliance chain, from inspections and investigations to prosecution and adjudication.</p>
<p>Description of Activities / Actions Implemented</p>	<p>Good practice consists in the establishment and operation of EnviCrimeNet as a permanent, structured and practitioner-driven European network for strategic coordination against environmental crime. EnviCrimeNet functions as a platform that connects law enforcement authorities, criminal investigators and prosecutors specialized in environmental crime, enabling a coherent and coordinated response across Member States to crimes that are often complex, transnational and linked to organized criminal networks.</p> <p>This good practice is based on a strategic, non-operational cooperation model. Instead of replacing national competences, EnviCrimeNet strengthens them by facilitating the exchange of expertise, intelligence insights, investigative approaches and lessons learned. The network supports practitioners in identifying emerging crime patterns, understanding regulatory gaps, and improving investigative and prosecutorial strategies related to environmental crime, including illegal waste trafficking, wildlife crime, biodiversity loss, pollution offences and climate-related crimes.</p> <p>A key element of this good practice is the institutional integration of EnviCrimeNet within the EU security framework through Europol, which acts as the network’s Secretariat. This ensures continuity, credibility and alignment with EU priorities on serious and organized crime. Through this arrangement, EnviCrimeNet contributes to EU-level strategic processes such as EMPACT, threat assessments and policy discussions, helping to elevate environmental crime from a marginal issue to a recognized security and rule-of-law priority.</p> <p>Another defining feature of good practice is its multi-network approach. EnviCrimeNet works in close cooperation with IMPEL (environmental authorities), ENPE (prosecutors) and EUFJE (judges), covering the full environmental compliance chain. This cooperation enables a holistic approach in which administrative enforcement, criminal investigation, prosecution and judicial practice are mutually reinforced. Joint conferences, statements, training activities and methodological tools illustrate how this coordinated model translates into practical improvements on the ground.</p> <p>The good practice also includes capacity building and knowledge development, through the drafting of common investigative principles, manuals and guidance documents, as well as training activities in cooperation with CEPOL and other partners. These actions support law enforcement authorities in addressing complex investigations, including financial aspects of environmental crime, cyber-enabled offences and transboundary cases.</p>
<p>Results and Achievements</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Institutional consolidation of EnviCrimeNet as a legally established European non-profit association. • Development of harmonized investigative principles and a shared criminal investigation manual. • Enhanced cross-border cooperation among law enforcement agencies across the EU.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delivery of specialized training activities improving investigative and analytical capacities. • Strategic advisory contributions to key EU legislative and policy initiatives. • Expansion of EnviCrimeNet’s cooperation beyond the EU, fostering global enforcement synergies.
Success factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formal EU-level recognition by the Council of the European Union, ensuring legitimacy and strategic authority. • Strong institutional anchoring within Europol, providing stability, coordination and alignment with EU security priorities. • Practitioner-led network composed of specialized law enforcement authorities and criminal investigators. • Clear strategic (non-operational) mandate, fostering trust, information exchange and participation among Member States. • Close cooperation with complementary enforcement and judicial networks (IMPEL, ENPE, EUFJE), covering the entire compliance chain.
Supporting Documents or Links	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • https://www.envicrimenet.eu/ • https://webgate.ec.europa.eu/life/publicWebsite/project/LIFE20-PRE-ES-000001/fight-against-environmental-crime-at-a-strategic-level-through-the-strengthening-of-envicrimenet-network-of-experts-in-environmental-criminal-investigations